

1 **Closed-loop modulation of local slow oscillations in human NREM sleep**

2 Authors: Simon Ruch^{1,2,3*}, Flavio Jean Schmidig^{2,3}, Leona Knüsel², Katharina Henke^{2,4}

3

4 ¹ Institute for Neuromodulation and Neurotechnology,
5 Department of Neurosurgery and Neurotechnology,
6 University Hospital and University of Tuebingen,
7 Otfried-Müller-Str. 45, Tübingen 72076, Germany.

8 ² Cognitive Neuroscience of Memory and Consciousness
9 Institute of Psychology, University of Bern, Fabrikstrasse 8, 3012 Bern, Switzerland.

10 ³ These authors contributed equally

11 ⁴ Senior author

12

13 ***Corresponding author and lead contact:**

14 Dr. Simon Ruch
15 Institute for Neuromodulation and Neurotechnology,
16 Department of Neurosurgery and Neurotechnology,
17 University Hospital and University of Tuebingen,
18 Otfried-Müller-Str. 45, Tübingen 72076, Germany
19 simon.ruch@uni-tuebingen.de

20

21 Manuscript version: February 23, 2022

1 Abstract

22
23 Slow-wave sleep is the deep non-rapid eye-movement (NREM) sleep stage that is most relevant for the
24 recuperative function of sleep. Its defining property is the presence of slow oscillations (<2 Hz) in the scalp
25 electroencephalogram (EEG). Slow oscillations are generated by a synchronous back and forth between highly
26 active UP-states and silent DOWN-states in neocortical neurons. Growing evidence suggests that closed-loop
27 sensory stimulation targeted at UP-states of EEG-defined slow oscillations can enhance the slow oscillatory
28 activity, increase sleep depth, and boost sleep's recuperative functions. However, several studies failed to
29 replicate such findings. Failed replications might be due to the use of conventional closed-loop stimulation
30 algorithms that analyze the signal from one single electrode and thereby neglect the fact that slow oscillations
31 vary with respect to their origins, distributions, and trajectories on the scalp. In particular, conventional
32 algorithms nonspecifically target functionally heterogeneous UP-states of distinct origins. After all, slow
33 oscillations at distinct sites of the scalp have been associated with distinct functions. Here we present a novel
34 EEG-based closed-loop stimulation algorithm that allows targeting UP- and DOWN-states of distinct cerebral
35 origins based on topographic analyses of the EEG: the topographic targeting of slow oscillations (TOPOSO)
36 algorithm. We present evidence that the TOPOSO algorithm can detect and target local slow oscillations with
37 specific, predefined voltage maps on the scalp in real-time. Compared to conventional algorithms TOPOSO
38 leads to fewer but locally more specific stimulations in a simulation study. In a validation study with napping
39 participants, TOPOSO targets auditory stimulation reliably at local UP-states over frontal, sensorimotor, and
40 centro-parietal regions. Importantly, auditory stimulation temporarily enhanced the targeted local state.
41 However, stimulation then elicited a standard frontal slow oscillation rather than local slow oscillations. The
42 TOPOSO algorithm is suitable for the modulation and the study of the functions of local slow oscillations.

43
44 **Keywords:** slow-wave sleep, NREM, eeg, closed-loop stimulation, local sleep

2 Introduction

45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65
66
67
68
69
70
71
72
73
74
75
76
77
78
79
80
81
82

Slow-wave sleep (SWS) is the deep, restorative sleep stage that helps us to recover from our daily activity. It is vital for our mental and physical health. Prolonged complete suppression of SWS leads to severe health issues and ultimately death (Llorens et al., 2017; Rechtschaffen et al., 2002). Recent research has provided groundbreaking insights into the processes and mechanisms by which SWS contributes to health. First of all, SWS was found to help maintain synaptic homeostasis (Tononi & Cirelli, 2020). During SWS, unused and obsolete synaptic connections are down-scaled to compensate for the net synaptic growth and potentiation that occurred during prior wakefulness. This process prevents excessive synaptic potentiation, reduces the signal-to-noise ratio of neuronal activity, and thereby renews our learning capacity. Slow-wave sleep was further found to contribute to memory consolidation by allowing memories that were formed during the day to be reactivated and replayed in the absence of other ongoing cognitive activity. Repeated memory reactivation during sleep strengthens the replayed memories and integrates them into existing knowledge (Klinzing et al., 2019; Rasch & Born, 2013). Further functions that have been associated with SWS are removal of metabolic waste from the brain (Xie et al., 2013), cellular and DNA repair in the brain (Vyazovskiy & Harris, 2013; Zada et al., 2019), and even the formation of immunological memory (Besedovsky et al., 2012).

Recent insights into the mechanisms and functions of slow-wave sleep have led to a quest for tools to enhance this precious sleep stage in order to boost its effects on cognition and health (Choi et al., 2020; Geiser et al., 2020; Grimaldi et al., 2020; Scholes et al., 2020; Talamini & Juan, 2020; Wunderlin et al., 2021). Interestingly, sensory and especially auditory stimulation during sleep can be used to entrain and enhance the slow oscillatory electric activity in the EEG that defines SWS. During SWS, cortical neurons oscillate between hyperpolarized and therefore inactive “DOWN”-states, and depolarized and highly active “UP”-states. Both states last between 0.25 and 1 s each. The back and forth between these two states occurs in a highly synchronized manner which induces strong electrical fields that manifest in the scalp EEG as slow oscillations with frequencies between 0.5 and 2 Hz (Iber et al., 2007). Hence the term slow-wave sleep. There is compelling evidence that sensory - especially auditory - stimulation temporarily enhances the slow oscillatory activity during sleep if stimulation is applied during the EEG-defined “UP”-state (Danilenko et al., 2020; Ngo et al., 2015; Santostasi et al., 2016). UP-targeted stimulation probably increases the synchronicity between neurons’ back and forth between UP- and DOWN-states.

UP-state targeted closed-loop auditory stimulation during sleep was not only found to temporarily enhance slow oscillations in the EEG, but to boost the cognitive and biological functions of SWS. Several studies suggested that closed-loop auditory stimulation can improve overnight memory retention in young (Ngo, Martinetz, et al., 2013; Ong et al., 2016) and old (Papalambros et al., 2017) adults. Other studies reported improved hippocampus-dependent learning on the next day (Ong et al., 2018) - probably due to enhanced synaptic down-scaling during sleep. A full night of UP-state targeted auditory stimulation was also found to improve immune function (Besedovsky et al., 2017) and autonomic regulation (Grimaldi et al., 2019).

Unfortunately, determining the presence of slow oscillations from the scalp EEG for targeting stimulation at neuronal UP-states is not trivial because slow oscillations are a heterogeneous phenomenon. High-density EEG recordings of sleep suggest that there exist different subtypes of slow oscillations - some

83 representing a global phenomenon on the scalp, and some being more local in that they only involve a few
84 electrodes (Bernardi et al., 2018). Slow oscillations further are not stationary but appear to travel across the
85 scalp (Massimini et al., 2004). Source modeling of sleep EEG recordings confirmed that single slow oscillations
86 have distinct origins and unique propagation patterns in the cortex (Murphy et al., 2009), and that different local
87 slow oscillations can coexist (Riedner et al., 2007). Intracranial recordings in humans further suggested that
88 most slow oscillations are a local rather than a brain-wide phenomenon (Mak-McCully et al., 2015; Nir et al.,
89 2011).

90 Different subtypes of slow oscillations might exert different functions in the brain. This is indirectly
91 suggested by the finding that the scalp distribution of spontaneous slow oscillatory activity during SWS mirrors
92 prior experience as well as individual differences in cognitive abilities (see e.g. Avvenuti & Bernardi, 2022 for
93 an up-to-date review on local sleep). For example, scalp maps of sleep slow oscillations change as a function of
94 prior learning - potentially due to local changes in the need for synaptic renormalization (Huber et al., 2004,
95 2006) as well as due to locally restricted neuronal activity related to the consolidation of newly acquired skills
96 and memories (Fattinger et al., 2017; Mascetti et al., 2013). Slow oscillations are thus locally regulated in a use-
97 dependent manner (Avvenuti & Bernardi, 2022). The topographic pattern of slow oscillatory activity is further
98 known to change throughout adolescence (Kurth et al., 2010, 2012; Ringli & Huber, 2011) and with aging
99 (Landolt & Borbély, 2001; Sprecher et al., 2016), and these changes are associated with skill maturation in
100 adolescents (Kurth et al., 2012), and presumably with cognitive decline (Mander et al., 2013, 2017) in the
101 elderly. Finally, different individuals show unique but stable, trait-like topographic distributions of slow
102 oscillatory activity that might reflect individual differences in brain organization and function (Markovic et al.,
103 2018). Successful enhancement or modulation of specific sleep functions by means of closed-loop stimulation
104 might thus require stimulation techniques that are capable of precise targeting of the relevant local slow-
105 oscillations.

106 To the best of our knowledge, all existing EEG-based algorithms for slow oscillation phase-targeted
107 stimulation ignore the fact that slow oscillations are a spatially heterogeneous phenomenon. All currently used
108 algorithms analyze the signal from one single location (one single electrode, e. g. Fz, or the average signal from
109 a patch of neighboring electrodes) referenced to pooled mastoids (standard reference in sleep research) to
110 determine the current phase of ongoing slow oscillations and to predict and target upcoming “UP-” and
111 “DOWN-” states (Cox et al., 2014; Ngo et al., 2015; Santostasi et al., 2016; Sousouri et al., 2021). Single-
112 channel EEG provides little information about the location and the polarity of the neuronal generator of a wave-
113 form, i.e. about where in the brain a slow oscillation is most prominent, and whether the involved neurons are in
114 an UP- or in a DOWN-state. Existing algorithms thus most likely target a very heterogeneous set of slow
115 oscillations with different scalp maps and distinct cortical origins and trajectories. The fate of a phase-targeted
116 stimulus, i.e. whether and where it elicits (or interrupts) a slow oscillation in the brain, might not only depend on
117 the phase of ongoing slow oscillations (Schabus et al., 2012), but also on their origin in the brain (Sousouri et
118 al., 2021).

119 Although some studies observed that UP-state targeted auditory stimulation can improve the cognitive
120 and health benefits of SWS, other studies failed to replicate these findings (Henin et al., 2019; Wunderlin et al.,
121 2021). For example, older adults showed reduced entrainment and enhancement of slow oscillations during

122 stimulation (Schneider et al., 2020) and their overnight memory consolidation did not improve with stimulation
123 (Papalambros et al., 2019; Schneider et al., 2020; Wunderlin et al., 2021). The contradictory findings on the
124 effect of UP-state targeted stimulation could result from the fact that studies did not take into account the
125 heterogeneous nature of slow oscillations. If, for example, slow oscillatory patterns during SWS change
126 throughout adolescence (Kurth et al., 2010, 2012; Ringli & Huber, 2011) and with age (Landolt & Borbély,
127 2001; Sprecher et al., 2016), the same stimulation algorithm might target different UP-states and thus yield
128 different effects on sleep's functions in children, young adults, and the elderly.

129 Phase-targeted stimulation might provide more consistent insights into the function of sleep and might
130 yield more reliable and replicable effects on behavior if only those subtypes of local slow oscillations were
131 targeted that are thought to be relevant for a specific research question or a specific aim. For example, phase-
132 dependent stimulation might improve the consolidation of a newly learned motor skill during sleep following
133 learning only if stimulation targets slow oscillations in the motor cortex (Fattinger et al., 2017; Huber et al.,
134 2004). We suggest that specific local slow oscillations can be identified and targeted by analyzing the temporal
135 evolution of the voltage distribution in the scalp EEG, i.e. the scalp maps, instead of or in addition to the wave-
136 form of the voltage of single channels. Although determining the exact cortical source of an EEG signal is non-
137 trivial, there is agreement that specific, recurring and temporarily stable scalp maps must reflect specific brain
138 states that can be attributed to specific neuronal processes (Michel & Koenig, 2018). These maps can be targeted
139 in real-time in closed-loop applications (Diaz Hernandez et al., 2016).

140 We propose a novel closed-loop stimulation algorithm that predicts and targets upcoming local UP-
141 and DOWN-states of slow oscillations with high temporal and topographic precision: the topographic targeting
142 of slow oscillations (TOPOSO) algorithm. Local UP-/DOWN-states are defined as peaks/troughs of scalp EEG
143 oscillations between 0.5 to 2 Hz that are most prominent over a specific region of interest on the scalp (e.g. over
144 electrode Fz, which would be stereotypical frontal slow oscillations (Massimini et al., 2004), or electrode C4,
145 which would be slow-oscillations in the right sensorimotor cortex (Krugliakova et al., 2020)). To target such
146 UP-/DOWN-states, the TOPOSO algorithm continuously assesses the similarity between the current voltage
147 distribution of the EEG on the scalp and the voltage distribution of precomputed template maps of the targeted
148 UP- or DOWN-states. The algorithm aims to detect transitions into local UP-/DOWN-states based on the
149 temporal evolution of the similarity between EEG scalp maps and template maps and on the wave-form of the
150 EEG signal over the targeted locus. The algorithm is supposed to detect transitions into local UP- or DOWN-
151 states with well defined scalp maps in near real time and to leave enough time to trigger stimulation at the actual
152 peak of the upcoming UP- or DOWN-state. In simulations performed on pre-recorded data, we assessed whether
153 using scalp maps in addition to single-channel data leads to fewer but more precise stimulations. In a sham-
154 controlled within-subject experiment, we explored whether we are able to target auditory stimulations at local
155 UP-states over different cortical regions (Fz, C4, CPz). We assessed the impact of auditory stimulation on the
156 targeted local UP-state and explored whether stimulation would induce subsequent local slow oscillations over
157 the targeted sites. TOPOSO targeted auditory stimulation reliably at local UP-states over frontal, sensorimotor,
158 and centro-parietal regions and temporarily enhanced the targeted local state. The stimulation used here elicited
159 – due to its auditory nature – a standard frontal slow oscillation rather than local slow oscillations.

160

3 Description of the TOPOSO algorithm

161 3.1 Aim and rationale

162 Local slow oscillations are generated by a highly coordinated back and forth between depolarized UP-
163 and hyperpolarized DOWN-phases of the neurons within a specific, isolated cortical region or network (Nir et
164 al., 2011). Here, it is assumed that the electric fields induced by the coordinated UP- and DOWN-phases of
165 these specific neurons yield scalp maps that have a high spatial similarity but show inverse polarities, i.e. scalp
166 maps that are anticorrelated. Local slow oscillations should thus manifest as sequences of prominent, highly
167 similar, anticorrelated scalp maps with well-defined transitions between these states. Previous work indeed
168 suggested that UP- and DOWN-states of auditory evoked frontal slow oscillation show highly similar but
169 anticorrelated maps ($r > |-.95|$, see supplementary table S6 in Züst et al., 2019). During a local slow-oscillation,
170 the correlation between EEG scalp maps and the predefined scalp map of a specific target state (e.g. an UP-state
171 over the motor cortex) should thus initially be highly negative (preceding DOWN-state), but should rapidly
172 transition to a highly positive correlation (target UP-state). This rapid transition should occur during a time-
173 window representative of $\frac{1}{4}$ to $\frac{1}{2}$ of the wavelength of slow-oscillations. By detecting such rapid transitions in
174 real time, it should be possible to predict and target upcoming local- UP- or DOWN-states. Here, transitions are
175 detected whenever the correlation between the current scalp EEG map and the scalp map of the predefined map
176 of the target state is negative but is rapidly increasing in a slow-oscillation specific time window, and the
177 voltage of the EEG over the target region is negative but increasing for transitions to UP-states, or positive but
178 decreasing for transitions to DOWN-states.

179 The TOPOSO algorithm builds on the assumption that template maps, which are representative of
180 specific targeted local slow oscillation UP- and DOWN-states, can be obtained from training data by post-hoc
181 detecting slow oscillations in the respective EEG channel. Maps are generated by averaging the scalp maps of
182 single UP-/DOWN states of only the most prominent (high-amplitude) slow oscillations that were post-hoc
183 identified over respective target electrodes (e.g. Fz, see Fig. 7 for examples of template maps; see chapter 3.3 for
184 template generation). Template maps can be obtained either from sleep data of a baseline night of the same
185 subject, or from sleep data of a representative sample of subjects. The resulting maps can be used to assess how
186 the similarity between real-time EEG data and a specific map evolves in time. A rapid and consistent increase in
187 similarity should indicate an upcoming local UP- or DOWN-state.

188 The TOPOSO algorithm detects a transition into an upcoming UP- (or DOWN-) state if the following
189 conditions are fulfilled: (A) the similarity between the actual scalp EEG map and the scalp map of the target UP-
190 (DOWN-) state is constantly increasing but (B) is still negative for the majority of the recent data samples; (C)
191 the mean voltage over electrodes at the target site (e.g. Fz) is increasing (decreasing for DOWN-states) but (D)
192 is still negative (positive) for the majority of the recent samples.

193 To detect transitions into UP-/DOWN-states, the TOPOSO algorithm analyzes the temporal evolution
194 of the real time EEG in a data window with a duration that is based on the prototypical frequency of slow
195 oscillations. Human slow oscillations peak at frequencies between 0.5- 1.0 Hz (Achermann & Borbély, 1997),
196 which yields a duration of about 500 ms between peaks of consecutive UP- and DOWN-states at the upper
197 frequency boundary. The time sequence between two states (e.g. from DOWN- to UP-state; see Figure 1) can be

198 divided in 4 time windows: (1) post-peak, (2) pre-zero-crossing (highlighted in Figure 1, left panel), (3) post-
 199 zero-crossing, and (4) pre-peak. The earliest possible time window for reliably detecting a transition is at the
 200 zero-crossing, i.e. by analyzing the pre-zero-crossing time window. At frequencies of 0.5-1 Hz, the pre-zero-
 201 crossing time window is expected to have a minimal duration of about 125 ms. This corresponds to 1/8th of the
 202 wavelength at 1 Hz. Therefore, the most recent 122 ms of real-time EEG data are used for detecting transitions
 203 into UP-/DOWN- states (61 samples at 500 Hz sampling rate).

204 The TOPOSO algorithm operates on unfiltered EEG data. Preprocessing only involves the following
 205 steps: removal of EOG-, EMG-, and artifact-laden EEG-channels, de-trending of each single channel, and re-
 206 referencing to the common average. Then, the relevant features are extracted at every data sample: the voltage
 207 over the target electrode (or the average voltage of a set of target electrodes), and the correlation of the scalp
 208 map with the template map.

209

Figure 1: Visualization of the TOPOSO algorithm (a) and its implementation (b). a) the voltage over the target EEG channel and the similarity between the scalp EEG and the template scalp map (template correlation) for one slow oscillation. The DOWN-state, the transition between states, and the UP-state are highlighted. The grey bar indicates the time-window during which the transition into the UP-state is detected. The features used to detect the transition are illustrated as well. b) sketch of the implementation of the algorithm for closed-loop applications.

210

211 We expected that both the absolute amplitudes of the EEG and the correlation between EEG scalp
 212 maps and template maps would vary between subjects (due to differences in skin and skull conductivity, head
 213 geometry, neuroanatomy, and the fit of EEG caps). To reduce the influence of interindividual differences in
 214 signal quality on algorithm performance, only the sign (+/-) of the correlation/voltage at each time-point as well
 215 as the sign of the sample-to-sample change in correlation/voltage instead of absolute values is analyzed. The
 216 TOPOSO algorithm thus ignores the actual numeric values of the voltage and the correlation.

217 **3.2 Formal description**

218 Put formally, a transition into an UP- or a DOWN-state is detected if all four of the following
219 conditions are fulfilled.

220 (A) The correlation corr (similarity) between the EEG (S) and the template map T is increasing for at
221 least C_1 of the recent n samples:

$$222 \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \left(\frac{\text{corr}(S_{i+1}, T) - \text{corr}(S_i, T)}{|\text{corr}(S_{i+1}, T) - \text{corr}(S_i, T)|} * 0.5 + 0.5 \right)}{n-1} \geq C_1$$

223 (B) The correlation between the EEG (S) and the template map T is still negative for at least C_2 of the
224 recent n samples:

$$225 \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{p * (0 - \text{corr}(S_i, T))}{|0 - \text{corr}(S_i, T)|} * 0.5 + 0.5 \right)}{n} \geq C_2$$

226 (C) The voltage at the target site (referenced to the global average) is increasing for at least C_1 of the
227 recent n samples:

$$228 \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \left(\frac{v_{i+1} - v_i}{|v_{i+1} - v_i|} * 0.5 + 0.5 \right)}{n-1} \geq C_1$$

229 (D) The voltage is still negative for at least C_2 of the recent n samples:

$$230 \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{p * (0 - v_i)}{|0 - v_i|} * 0.5 + 0.5 \right)}{n} \geq C_2$$

231 Where n = number of samples (61) used for analysis, v_i = the voltage over the target electrode at
232 sample i , S_i = the vector with the voltage distribution (scalp map) over all electrodes at sample i , T = the vector
233 with the voltage distribution of the target state (template map), p = the polarity of the target state (= +1 for
234 transitions to UP-states, = -1 for transitions to DOWN-states), C_1 and C_2 = pre-defined criteria.

235 To find optimal parameters for C_1 and C_2 , we assessed how the TOPOSO algorithm would perform on
236 pre-recorded EEG data for all possible combinations of C_1 and C_2 . For each parameter combination, we
237 determined the average number of detected transitions into UP- and DOWN-states, the mean amplitude of the
238 target states, and the time between the detection of a transition and the actual amplitude peak. This was done
239 only for frontal slow oscillations, assuming that the parameters would work with other target regions as well.
240 Optimal parameters were $C_1 = 75\%$ and $C_2 = 50\%$.

241 **3.3 Template generation**242 **3.3.1 Procedure**

243 To assess whether meaningful and distinct scalp maps for local UP- and DOWN-states can be
244 generated, we first extracted scalp maps focused on the following 12 electrodes/regions on the 10-20 grid: Fz,
245 Cz, Pz, Oz, F5, F6, T7, T8, C5, C6, P5, P6 (Table 1). Template maps for local UP-/DOWN-states were
246 extracted from pre-recorded EEG data (for details about the data samples, see chapter 3.3.2).

247 First, EOG and EMG channels were removed and data were re-referenced to the global average, which
248 allowed us to retrieve the original reference at Fz. Next, the target signal was extracted by averaging the voltage
249 over electrodes centered around the site of interest (e.g. AF1, AFz, AF2, F3, Fz and F4 for the target Fz, Table
250 1). Using the average of a set of nearby electrodes instead of just one single electrode provides a more robust
251 signal. The target signal was bandpass filtered at 0.15 - 2 Hz. Then, all data segments containing NREM sleep
252 were selected. In these segments, we identified all data snippets between consecutive positive-to-negative zero
253 crossings as potential slow oscillations if the snippets had a duration between 0.9 and 2 s (reflecting oscillations
254 in the range between 0.5 to 1.11 Hz). Only candidate events with a trough-to-peak amplitude exceeding $\frac{2}{3}$ of the
255 trough-to-peak amplitudes of all candidate events were kept as slow oscillations. For each selected slow
256 oscillation, we determined the negative-to-positive zero-crossing as the center of the oscillation.

257 To generate scalp templates for UP- and DOWN-states, we bandpass filtered the raw EEG signal from
258 0.3 to 35 Hz, re-referenced it to the global average, and then extracted ERPs centered on the negative-to-positive
259 zero-crossing for each of the previously identified slow oscillations. For the UP-state template, we then
260 extracted the peak after the zero-crossing (about 0.5s later) in every identified slow oscillation. Similarly, for the
261 DOWN-state template, we extracted the trough before the zero-crossing (about 0.5s before) in every slow
262 oscillation. Scalp maps were computed by taking the average maps of all samples +/- 40 ms around the
263 trough/peak. The maps were normalized by dividing the voltage at each channel by the maximum absolute
264 voltage of all channels.

Table 1: Electrodes used for creating an average signal of the target site.

Target site	Electrodes centered around the target site
Fz	AF1, AFz, AF2, F3, Fz, F4
Cz	C3, C1, Cz, C2, C4
Pz	P3, Pz, P4, POz
Oz	O1, O11, Oz, O12, O2
F5	Fp1, F7, F5, F3, FC5
F6	Fp2, F8, F6, F4, FC6
T7	FT9, FT7, T7, TP7, TP9
T8	FT10, FT8, T8, TP8, TP10
C5	FC5, T7, C5, C3 CP5
C6	FC6, T8, C6, C4 CP6
P5	TP9, P7, P5, P3
P6	TP10, P8, P6, P4

Note: The target signal for each target site was extracted by averaging the voltage over the electrodes centered around the site of interest. Using the average of a set of nearby electrodes instead of just one single electrode provides a more robust signal.

265 **3.3.2 Origin of EEG data**

266 To create template maps for the detection of local UP-/DOWN-states, we used pre-recorded EEG data
 267 of N3 sleep. Data had been recorded during an afternoon nap in a sample of N = 39 participants (age = 19-32, M
 268 \pm SD = 23.4 \pm 3.5; 29 (74%) female) in a previous study on vocabulary learning during sleep (Züst et al., 2019).
 269 All participants were mentally and physically healthy and right-handed. Subjects were restricted to 4 h of sleep
 270 the night before the experiment. Sleep recordings started between 12:40 and 14:50 and lasted about 90 min (M \pm
 271 SD = 93.5 \pm 33.1 min). Participants were played pairs of foreign words and German words via headphones
 272 while asleep. For further details on the study procedure, see (Züst et al., 2019). Two subjects from the original
 273 study (N= 41) were excluded due to large signal drifts on a few electrodes.

274 **3.4 Template validation**

275 Visual inspection of the topographies of the UP- and DOWN-state templates that were extracted for the
 276 twelve target sites suggested that all templates reflected unique and highly distinct electrical fields (Figure 2, left
 277 panel). Inspection of the dipole fits for each template map confirmed that each template reflected a brain state
 278 that was most likely generated by a cortical dipole at the or close to the site of the target electrodes. Dipole
 279 fitting was performed for each template map assuming one single dipole. Fitting was done in fieldtrip, using the
 280 default boundary element method (bem) with the volume conduction model of the head that is provided by
 281 fieldtrip. This head model is based on the segmentation by Collins et al. (Collins et al., 1998) and was
 282 constructed as reported in Oostenveld (Oostenveld et al., 2003).

283

284 **4 Validation on pre-recorded data**

285 To assess the precision, reliability, and validity of the TOPOSO algorithm, we applied it to pre-
286 recorded EEG data. We simulated a real-time data stream using pre-recorded sleep EEG data from an
287 unpublished nap study and had our algorithm detect transitions into UP-states or DOWN-states. We did this
288 separately for each of the 12 selected target sites. We then analyzed the EEG data centered around the time
289 stamps of the detected transitions. We assessed whether the TOPOSO algorithm indeed detects time-points
290 during which the brain transitions into local UP- or DOWN-states with scalp maps that match the template of
291 the targeted states.

292 We further assessed whether using the similarity between scalp maps and template maps for detecting
293 transitions into local UP-/DOWN-states (template-based algorithm) improves the topographic precision
294 compared to conventional algorithms that only operate on a single EEG channel. To this aim, as a control
295 condition, we modified the TOPOSO algorithm to only use the voltage of the EEG of the target site for
296 detecting state transitions. We used this modified algorithm to detect transitions into UP-/DOWN-states in the
297 same pre-recorded EEG data.

298 **4.1 Method**

299 **4.1.1 Test sample**

300 The algorithm was tested on stage N3 sleep obtained from an additional set of pre-recorded EEG data
301 that had not been used to generate the template maps of target states (see chapter 3.3.2). This data has been
302 collected during an afternoon nap in a previously unreported sample of $N = 21$ (age = 18-28, $M \pm SD = 21.8 \pm$
303 2.6 ; 17 (81%) female) mentally and physically healthy participants. All participants were right-handed.
304 Participants were subjected to the same study protocol as the participants of the data used for template
305 generation (Züst et al., 2019).

306 **4.1.2 Procedure**

307 **4.1.2.1 Simulation of real-time detection of state transitions**

308 We preprocessed the pre-recorded EEG data to match the data as it would be processed in real-time
309 (de-trending, re-referencing to global average) and then applied the algorithm to all N3 segments of all data sets.
310 This procedure was performed separately for each of the 12 selected target sites and for UP- vs. DOWN-states.
311 All time points where the TOPOSO algorithm detected a transition into the specific UP-/DOWN-state were
312 marked for later analysis. The TOPOSO algorithm tended to repeatedly detect the transition into the same state
313 across multiple subsequent time points. Only the first time point of such sequences was selected for analysis.
314 Any additionally marked events within the next 800 ms were discarded (duration of a fast slow oscillation at 1.2
315 Hz) to avoid repeatedly sampling the same events.

316 To assess how the TOPOSO algorithm performs compared to conventional algorithms that only use a
317 single EEG channel (without topographic information) for detecting UP-/DOWN-states, we further ran
318 simulations with a modified version of our algorithm that only uses the voltage of the target site for detecting

319 state transitions. In this modified version, only conditions C and D (see “3.2 Formal description of the
320 algorithm”) had to be fulfilled for detecting a transition. We performed the same simulations (detection of
321 UP-/DOWN-states at 12 selected target sites) as with the original version of our algorithm and compared the
322 EEG between transitions detected between simulations.

323 **4.1.2.2 Analysis of the detected state transitions**

324 For each detected transition, we extracted the event-related EEG centered around +/- 1 s of the
325 transition. We computed the mean event-related potential (ERP), the mean correlation between the raw EEG and
326 the template map, as well as the global field power (GFP) of the mean ERP for each subject and each condition
327 (UP-/DOWN-state and each site). These analyses were performed on bandpass filtered EEG signals (0.3 - 35
328 Hz). No further preprocessing was done.

329 **4.2 Results**

330 **4.2.1 Successful detection of transitions into local UP-/DOWN-states**

331 Visual inspection of ERP topographies revealed that the TOPOSO algorithm indeed detects transitions
332 into the targeted local state (Figure 2; due to space limitations, figures only illustrate the results of UP-state
333 targets. Results are reported for both, UP- and DOWN-state targets, in the text. Supplementary Figures 1-3
334 illustrate the results of DOWN-state targets).

335 The time courses of the EEG, the GFP of the mean EEG and the correlation between EEG and template
336 map indicate that the target state peaked at about 200 ms after the detected transition (Figure 3, Supplementary
337 Figure 2 for DOWN-states). Interestingly, the transition was preceded by voltage distributions exactly opposing
338 the target state. I.e., if the target state was a local peak, the detected transitions into this local peak were
339 preceded by a local trough at the same target region at about -200 ms before the transition (Figure 3,
340 Supplementary Figure 2 for DOWN-states). Furthermore, the half-wave which followed the detected transition
341 and which peaked at the target site lasted on average about 500 ms, indicating that the detected events are parts
342 of oscillatory patterns with a frequency of 1Hz. Taken together, these observations provide strong evidence that
343 the TOPOSO algorithm responds to events that represent UP- and DOWN-states of slow oscillations.

344

Figure 2: Topographies of each targeted UP-state (template map in normalized units, left) and the average EEG topography over all trials displayed from 0.4s before to 0.4s after the detection of a transition ($t=0$), separately for each target site (ERP in μV). The EEG was averaged across ± 50 ms for each depicted time-point. The high similarity of the template map and the targeted brain state 200 ms (highlighted) after the detection of a transition suggests precise targeting of local UP-states.

345

346

347

Figure 3: Event-related EEG activity relative to the detection of the transition ($t = 0$) into a local UP-state for each of the twelve target sites (color coded): a) event-related potential (μV) at the target site, b) correlation of the EEG with the template map, and d) global field power (GFP in μV) of the EEG. The ERP and the correlation with the template map reveal a similar prediction for each of the twelve target sites. Grey shades mark the time window (100 ms - 300 ms post transition) used for the analysis of the peak EEG.

348

349 For both, the conventional algorithm and the TOPOSO algorithm, statistical assessment of the mean
 350 response over a 200 ms time window between 0.1 and 0.3 s following the detection of transition revealed that
 351 the mean ERP of the corresponding target channel differed significantly from 0. This was the case for DOWN-
 352 state targets as well as for UP-state targets. The same pattern was found for the mean correlation between the
 353 EEG scalp map and the template map (all $t(20) > 13$, all $p < .001$).

354 **4.2.2 Higher topographic precision than conventional algorithms**

355 The TOPOSO algorithm is more selective and more precise in predicting the targeted brain states than
 356 conventional algorithms that operate on the voltage of single, local EEG channels. This was suggested by direct
 357 comparisons of transitions detected with the TOPOSO algorithm vs. the modified algorithm that is based
 358 exclusively on the voltage of local EEG channels (Figure 4, Supplementary Figure 3 for DOWN-states). The
 359 TOPOSO algorithm detected significantly fewer transitions into UP-/DOWN-states, but the UP-/DOWN-states
 360 that followed the transitions had higher amplitudes at the target site, stronger correlations with the target
 361 templates, and higher GFP compared to states that followed transitions detected with the EEG (all paired-sample
 362 t-tests: $t(20) > 3.4$, $p < 0.003$). ERPs, correlations, and the GFP averaged over the time from 100 to 300 ms post
 363 transition were compared separately for each state (UP/DOWN) and each target site.

364

Figure 4: Comparison between the template-based TOPOSO algorithm (Template) and a conventional single-EEG-channel-based (EEG) algorithm for UP-state targeting: a) mean voltage (ERP in μV) at the target site (mean over adjacent electrodes), b) correlation between EEG scalp map and template map, and c) global field power (all averaged across the time window from 0.1. to 0.3 s after detection of a transition) as well as d) the number of predicted states per minute. Each panel displays mean and standard error of the mean (error bars) for each target site. All paired-samples contrasts for each target were significant at $p < .003$.

365 **4.3 Discussion**

366 We assessed whether our newly proposed TOPOSO algorithm could be used in real-time to predict and
 367 target stimulation at UP- and DOWN-states of local slow oscillations during sleep. To this aim, we performed
 368 simulations on pre-recorded EEG data in which we used our algorithm to target local up- and DOWN-states
 369 over 12 different sites on the scalp.

370 We found that the TOPOSO algorithm detects transitions into brain states with scalp maps that are
 371 highly similar to the template maps of the targeted UP-/DOWN-states, and that are highly distinct from non-
 372 targeted templates (Figure 2, Supplementary Figure 1 for DOWN-states). Importantly, these brain states peak at
 373 about 200 ms after detection of the transitions, which would provide enough time to trigger stimulation during
 374 the target state in real-time applications. The targeted brain-states have a duration of about 500 ms, which
 375 reflects half-waves of oscillatory events with a duration of ~ 1 s or a frequency of ~ 1 Hz, i.e. the frequency of
 376 human slow oscillations (Achermann & Borbély, 1997). Hence the TOPOSO algorithm appears suitable for
 377 real-time applications targeting local slow oscillations during sleep.

378 In comparison to a single-channel based algorithm, the TOPOSO algorithm detects fewer transitions
 379 into target states, but the detected states are more homogeneous and more similar to the targeted states with
 380 respect to their scalp maps. Thus, due to its topographic specificity, the TOPOSO algorithm might be more
 381 suitable than conventional algorithms for closed-loop applications aimed at targeting local slow oscillations.

382

5 Validation in a real-time application

383

384

385

386

387

388

389

390

391

To assess the usefulness of the TOPOSO algorithm in a real closed-loop stimulation application, we performed a within-subject sham controlled study in which we tried to target UP-states of local slow oscillations over three distinct sites on the scalp. We tested whether the TOPOSO algorithm can be used in vivo in real-time for targeting auditory stimulation at local UP-states. The goal was to assess how precise the TOPOSO algorithm is at targeting local slow oscillations at the intended phase, i.e. the UP-state. A further aim was to investigate the immediate impact of auditory stimulation on the targeted local UP-state, and to assess the influence of auditory stimulation on ensuing slow oscillatory and spindle activity, i.e. whether stimulation would be followed by additional local slow oscillations and local spindles at the targeted site.

392

393

394

395

396

397

398

399

400

401

402

403

404

405

406

407

408

409

410

411

412

413

Local UP-states were targeted over the frontal (Fz), right central (C4), and centro-parietal (CPz) cortex in a within-subject sham-controlled study design. The frontal cortex was selected because the majority of slow oscillations tend to originate in prefrontal regions (Finelli et al., 2001; Nir et al., 2011), because frontal slow oscillations have been proposed to be most relevant in memory consolidation (Klinzing et al., 2019; Ngo, Martinetz, et al., 2013), because frontal slow oscillations tend to govern sensory processing and even learning during sleep (Andrillon et al., 2016; Züst et al., 2019), and because most studies using phase-targeted closed-loop auditory stimulation focused on this region (Cox et al., 2014; Göldi et al., 2019; Ngo, Claussen, et al., 2013; Ngo et al., 2015; Ngo, Martinetz, et al., 2013; Santostasi et al., 2016; Shimizu et al., 2018). The right-central electrode C4 was chosen due to its proximity to the sensorimotor cortex. Fattinger et al. reported that auditory stimulation targeted at the DOWN-state of slow oscillations detected over the left motor cortex perturbed local but not global slow oscillatory activity at the targeted site (Fattinger et al., 2017). Importantly, perturbation of local slow oscillations was associated with impaired performance in a right-hand motor learning on the next day. Krugliakova et al. further suggested that UP-state targeted stimulation focusing on slow oscillations over the right motor cortex (C4) globally enhanced delta, theta, and sigma activity but also induced local changes in delta-sigma coupling in the right hemisphere (Krugliakova et al., 2020). These studies provide first evidence that local manipulation of sleep slow oscillations in the motor cortex is feasible and alters the local functions of sleep. The centro-parietal electrode CPz was selected because slow oscillations over this cortical region have been associated with absence of dreams during NREM sleep. Two studies investigating dreaming during NREM sleep revealed that humans are less likely to report dreams if wakened from NREM sleep that is dominated by high slow-wave activity over centroparietal regions (Siclari et al., 2017, 2018). Targeting and manipulating slow oscillations over these regions might thus provide a means to alter the frequency, vividness, or even content of dreams during NREM sleep.

414

5.1 Method

415

5.1.1 Implementation of the algorithm

416

417

418

Data was recorded using the BrainVision Recorder software v2.0 by Brain Products. This software provides a remote data access (RDA) server that allows streaming data in realtime (in 5-sample data blocks) via TCP/IP protocol.

419

The TOPOSO algorithm was implemented in MATLAB and was running on a second computer that

MODULATION OF LOCAL SLOW OSCILLATIONS

420 was connected to the recording computer via LAN cable. On this second computer, the “rda2ft” interface
 421 provided by fieldtrip streamed the real-time data to a buffer, from which it was read into a MATLAB instance
 422 which was running the detection algorithm. The TOPOSO algorithm continuously scanned the buffer for new
 423 data, and performed the necessary operations to detect transitions into UP-states of interest. Upon every
 424 detection of a transition, an event marker was written to a second fieldtrip buffer. A second MATLAB instance
 425 monitored this second buffer in realtime and triggered stimulation according to the current condition
 426 (stimulation vs. sham, with the respective target site and their specific delay). Sound onset and the EEG-marker
 427 were timely paired. Unfortunately, the EEG recording system did not allow to eliminate all time jitters, with
 428 which a jitter of up to 40 ms remained.

429 Stimulation was carried out in blocks, i.e. stimulation targeted the same site (Fz, C4, CPz, sham) five
 430 times in sequence before moving to the next site. Once five stimulations were applied for the specific template
 431 (5 for each template in sham), or if more than 2 minutes passed without stimulation, the algorithm moved on to
 432 the next block. All 4 blocks were repeated for as long as possible, with shuffled block order for each repetition
 433 (Figure 5). This procedure ensured that a similar amount of stimulations was achieved for each condition within
 434 each participant independent of the absolute amount of stimulations.

435 Each stimulus presentation was followed by a timeout of 2 s before the next sound could be played.
 436 Hence, the shortest possible time interval between consecutive stimulations was 2 s. This allowed for an
 437 unconfounded analysis of the impact of stimulation on the targeted slow oscillation UP-state and the ensuing
 438 slow oscillatory activity.

439

440 *Figure 5: Illustration of blocks of auditory stimulations targeting UP-states over different sites on the scalp (Fz, C4, CPz). Stimulation condition (Fz/C4/CPz) was switched after 5 successful stimulations in a given condition or if no stimulations occurred in more than 120 s.*

441

442 The average loop-time, i.e. the time it took the TOPOSO algorithm to analyze the EEG data, detect a
 443 target event, and trigger stimulus presentation, was 98 ± 20 ms ($M \pm SD$). Because the algorithm detected
 444 transitions into UP- or DOWN-states that peak about 200 ms after this transition, an additional delay of ~ 100
 445 ms was added to the loop time of 98 ms before playing the click noise to hit the peak of the target state.
 446 Importantly, the average delay between the transition time point and the actual UP-state peak seemed to vary
 447 between target sites. Simulations performed on the $N = 21$ pre-recorded datasets suggested that the average

448 delay was 200 ms for Fz, 180 ms for C4, and 215 ms for CPz. Therefore a delay of 100 ms for Fz, 80 ms for C4,
449 and 115 ms for CPz was added to the loop time of 98 ms before playing the click noise.

450 **5.1.2 Data collection**

451 **5.1.2.1 Participants**

452 Twenty mentally and physically healthy subjects were recruited to participate in this study. The
453 research protocol was approved by the institutional review board of the University of Bern, and informed
454 consent was obtained from each participant. Eight participants failed to reach stable slow-wave sleep during the
455 afternoon nap, leading to twelve remaining participants in the study (age = 23-31, $M \pm SD = 26.75 \pm 2.45$, 6
456 (50%) female).

457 **5.1.2.2 Procedure**

458 A short prescreening was performed during recruiting to exclude candidates with mental or physical
459 health issues from participation. Participants were asked to sleep not more than 4 hours in the night prior to the
460 experiment and to send a text message at the time they went to bed and at the time they got up to confirm
461 compliance. Furthermore, participants were asked to abstain from caffeine on the day of testing until after the
462 sleep recording. Participants arrived at the lab between noon and 2 pm, where the study procedure was
463 explained and they were asked to give informed written consent. Participants were outfitted with EEG caps and
464 with in-ear headphones (Pioneer, type SE-CL502_L) and were then asked to get prepared for taking a 90
465 minutes nap in a portable bed in the electromagnetically and acoustically shielded EEG cabin. Before lights
466 were turned off and participants were allowed to sleep, a hearing test was administered. In this test, short beeps
467 and tones were played at random intervals and randomly on the left or right ear. Participants indicated on which
468 ear they heard a tone by pressing the according buttons on a keyboard. Four different types of beeps of 50 ms
469 duration were presented: a pink noise tone, and pure tones with a frequency of 500 Hz, 1000 Hz and 2000 Hz.
470 Overall, 20 beeps in symmetrical steps between 15 and 45 dB(A) per frequency and per ear, leading to an
471 overall number of 160 beeps, were presented. The hearing test was implemented with the software
472 Presentation[®]. After the hearing test, the keyboard was removed and participants were asked to relax and, if
473 possible, sleep. Participants were informed that a click-sound similar to the pink noise played during the hearing
474 test would be presented during sleep. It was mentioned that stimulation only occurs during deep sleep and they
475 therefore should not aim to hear anything, because focusing on pending auditory stimuli might hamper sleep
476 quality. Afternoon naps started between 2 pm and 4 pm, and lasted about 85 min ($M = 85.5$, $SD = 21.6$). When
477 participants displayed stable NREM2 sleep, the experimenter initiated auditory stimulation. Initial stimulus
478 intensity was below the participant's hearing threshold but was increased within the first 10 – 20 stimulations.
479 Stimulus presentation was stopped, if the EEG revealed signs of arousal. When a subject returned to SWS,
480 auditory stimulation was resumed, typically starting with a ramp up of the signal intensity over the first 5 - 10
481 stimulations. If a participant failed to (re-)enter SWS after 80 mins, the EEG recording was stopped. Only
482 participants with at least 10 valid stimulations per condition were included in the data analysis ($n = 12$).

483 **5.1.2.3 EEG/Polysomnography**

484 EEG was recorded using 64 channel BrainCaps MR caps with sintered Ag/AgCl Multitrodes by
485 EASYCAP (www.easycap.de) and two 32 channel amplifiers from BrainAmp (www.brainproducts.com). Two
486 channels were used to assess eye movements, and one channel was used to assess the muscle tonus below the
487 chin. The reference electrode was positioned at Fz, and the ground electrode at CPz. Impedances were kept < 20
488 k Ω . The software BrainVision Recorder (www.brainproducts.com) was used to record the EEG data. All signals
489 were sampled at 500 Hz. Online polysomnographic visualization was performed according to AASM guidelines
490 using the OpenViBE environment (Renard et al., 2010).

491 **5.1.3 Data analysis**

492 **5.1.3.1 Offline sleep-scoring**

493 Offline sleep scoring was performed by two independent raters, according to AASM guidelines, using
494 the software Polyman (<http://www.edfplus.info/>). With a Cohen's K of .76, the rater agreement was substantial
495 (McHugh, 2012). For stimulus inclusion, only the distinction between deep NREM (N2, N3) and all other sleep
496 stages (awake, N1, REM) was of interest. In 12 of 3569 epochs (0.34 %), the raters disagreed in a way that was
497 potentially relevant for the inclusion of stimuli. In those 12 epochs, the score indicating the shallower sleep
498 stage was used.

499 **5.1.3.2 EEG pre-processing**

500 After removing EOG and EMG channels from the raw data, all EEG channels were re-referenced to the
501 common average. Next, the 50 Hz line noise and its harmonics was removed, and bad channels were identified
502 and interpolated using the PREP pipeline (Bigdely-Shamlo et al., 2015) as implemented in eeglab (Delorme &
503 Makeig, 2004). The cleaned EEG data was then again referenced to the global average and was bandpass
504 filtered between 0.25 and 100 Hz.

505 Artifact laden data segments were identified and marked for later exclusion, using a semi-automated
506 algorithm that was implemented in the fieldtrip toolbox (Oostenveld et al., 2011). Artifacts were identified
507 based on high-frequency noise (the boxcar-smoothed (window: 0.2 s) envelope of the 45-90 Hz frequency band
508 exceeded 5 standard deviations in any of the channels), signal jumps (the change in amplitude between two
509 consecutive samples exceeded 30 standard deviations in any of channel), rogue channels, e.g. due to sweating
510 (the minimal difference in voltage of any channel with all other channels exceeded 4 standard deviations), and
511 de-correlated signals (the difference between the actual data in a channel and its spherical interpolation
512 exceeded 4 standard deviations). Artifacts were padded by 0.5 s at both ends. The validity of this artifact
513 detection pipeline was confirmed by visual inspection.

514 Finally, EEG data was epoched from 2 s before to 2 s after stimulus onset for further analysis. For each
515 epoch, the time-course of the correlation between EEG scalp maps and template maps of the respective
516 condition was computed for additional analyses.

517 **5.1.3.3 Stimulus inclusion/exclusion**

518 Stimulations were considered valid if they occurred during NREM2 or NREM3 sleep, and in absence
 519 of EEG artifacts within +/- 3 s of stimulus onset. In addition, stimulations had to be presented with a minimal
 520 stimulus intensity of 37 dB(A) to be included in the data analysis. For an overview of the overall number of
 521 included stimulations per condition per participant, see Table 2. On average, we presented M = 41.67 (SD =
 522 27.23) click sounds per subject, of which 85.22% of stimuli were played in N3 (SD = 17.65 %).

Table 2: Average number of stimulations per condition

Condition	Fz	Fz sham	C4	C4 sham	CPz	CPz sham
average trials	42.17	42.92	40.5	39.92	41.83	42.67
SD	28.35	28.1	26.95	24.08	28.92	28.05

523 **5.1.3.4 Phase analysis**

524 To assess the accuracy of stimulation, the mean phase of the slow oscillation frequency band (< 4 Hz)
 525 was estimated for the time of stimulus onset. To this aim, the phase values of the Hilbert transform of the low-
 526 pass filtered (4 Hz) signal was extracted. The phase across all samples from 20 ms before to 20 ms after
 527 stimulus onset were averaged for each trial. This was done separately for the average signal of the respective
 528 target EEG channels as well as of the correlation between the EEG and the template map. Then, the mean phase
 529 for each experimental condition was computed separately for each participant.

530 **5.1.3.5 Current source density estimation**

531 Analyses of the post-stimulus ERP, the time-frequency decomposed signal, the post-stimulus power
 532 spectral density, and the post-stimulus phase-amplitude coupling were performed on current source density
 533 (CSD) estimates. CSD has the benefit that it provides a reference free signal with enhanced spatial resolution
 534 and specificity (Kayser & Tenke, 2015) compared to the raw EEG. CSD was estimated using the spherical
 535 spline method (Perrin et al., 1989, 1990) with default parameters as implemented in the fieldtrip toolbox (REF)
 536 for MATLAB.

537 **5.1.3.6 Time-frequency analysis**

538 Event-related spectral changes were compared between the different experimental conditions. To this
 539 aim, the spectral power was estimated from 2 Hz to 21 Hz at 1 Hz steps from 2 seconds before to 2 seconds after
 540 stimulus (40 ms steps, yielding a 25 Hz sampling rate) using discrete wavelet transformations. Transformations
 541 were performed with 3 wavelet cycles at the lowest frequency and a linear increase of 0.5 cycles per 1 Hz step
 542 to 12.5 cycles at the highest frequency. The resulting power time series were normalized for each frequency at
 543 the single-trial level by first z-standardizing the time-series at each frequency and then subtracting the mean
 544 normalized power from -2 to -1 seconds before stimulus onset. These standardized time-frequency
 545 decompositions were then averaged within each condition separately for each participant.

546 **5.1.3.7 Analysis of phase-amplitude coupling**

547 Post-stimulus phase-amplitude coupling (PAC) comodulograms were compared between experimental
 548 conditions for the phase of frequencies from 0.6 to 5 Hz (at 0.2 Hz steps) and the amplitude of frequencies
 549 between 4 and 40 Hz (at 1 Hz steps). De-biased PAC values as suggested by van Driel et al. (van Driel et al.,

550 2015) were computed for each phase-amplitude combination.

551 Phase values and amplitude envelopes were extracted for the data from 0 to 2 s after stimulus onset at
552 20 ms intervals (yielding a 50 Hz sampling rate) using discrete wavelet transformations. For phases,
553 transformations were performed with one cycle at the lowest frequency of 0.6 Hz and a linear increase of 0.2
554 cycles per 0.2 Hz step to 5.4 cycles at the highest frequency of 5 Hz. For amplitudes, transformations were
555 performed using 3 cycles at the lowest frequency of 4 Hz with a linear increase of 0.5 cycles per 1 Hz step to 21
556 cycles at the highest frequency of 40 Hz. The resulting PAC comodulograms were averaged within each
557 condition separately for each subject.

558 **5.1.3.8 Significance testing**

559 For each dependent measure (ERP, time-frequency decomposition, and phase amplitude coupling), the
560 impact of stimulation vs. sham was assessed separately for each target condition. Furthermore, the differential
561 effects of frontal vs. right central vs. centro-parietal targeted stimulation were assessed by comparing the
562 difference scores between stimulation vs. sham between all target sites using an omnibus test. Follow-up
563 contrasts were performed between each target site in case the omnibus test yielded a significant difference.

564 For the analysis of event-related potentials, topographic analyses of variance (TANOVA) were
565 performed as proposed by Koenig and colleagues (Koenig et al., 2011, 2013). Cluster-based corrections for
566 multiple comparisons in time were performed using 1000 permutations.

567 For all other analyses, mass univariate analyses (t-tests or ANOVAs) were performed with cluster-
568 based corrections for multiple comparisons using 1000 permutations (Maris & Oostenveld, 2007). Cluster-
569 formation threshold was set at $p < .05$ for all analyses. All tests were two-sided, clusters were said to be
570 significant at $\alpha < .05$.

571 **5.2 Results**

572 **5.2.1 Precise targeting of the peak phase**

573 First, we assessed how precise the TOPOSO algorithm was at targeting the peak phase, i.e. the peak of
574 the respective local UP-states. We extracted the mean slow-wave phase (<4 Hz) for the ERP over the site of
575 interest, as well as for the time-course of the correlation between the scalp map and the template map (Figure 6).

576 Phase distributions were significantly non-uniform for both the ERP and correlation with the template
577 maps for all targets (all $p < .01$, Hodges-Ajne omnibus-tests (Zar, 1999) as implemented in the CircStat toolbox
578 (Berens, 2009)). This suggests that the algorithm consistently targeted a specific phase. Stimulation preceded the
579 peak by $\sim 30^\circ$ (Table 3 and Figure 6) in all target conditions, both for the ERP and the correlation with the
580 template map. See Table 3 for mean phases and 95% confidence intervals of the phase (confidence intervals
581 were computed as suggested by (Zar, 1999) and as implemented in the CircStat Toolbox (Berens, 2009) for
582 MATLAB).

Table 3: Mean phase & 95% CI at stimulus onset (stimulation and sham) for the EEG at the target site and the for the correlation between EEG scalp maps and the template map, separately for each target site.

Target site	Mean phase (95% CI): EEG	Mean phase (95% CI): correlation
Fz	-28.55 (± 6.17)	-34.40 (± 6.07)
C4	-21.89 (± 9.36)	-24.51 (± 8.18)
CPz	-26.15 (± 6.94)	-26.28 (± 8.33)

583

584

585

Figure 6: Comparison of SO-phase and template map correlation between target sites. Upper row (target-eeg): Roseplots of phase of the target ERP with mean phase of each subject at the target site (red), mean phase across all subjects at target site (dark grey; vector-length = phase-coherence), 95% confidence interval around the group mean (light grey). Lower row (template-corr): Roseplots of phase of the template correlation with mean phase of each subject at the target site (red), mean phase across all subjects at target site (dark grey; vector-length = phase-coherence), 95% confidence interval around mean (light grey).

586

587 5.2.2 Stimulation temporarily enhances the targeted local UP-state

588 Previous studies suggest that closed-loop auditory stimulation targeting frontal UP-states briefly
 589 enhances the amplitude of the targeted state before inducing a frontal DOWN-state (e.g. Ngo et al., 2015; Ngo,
 590 Martinetz, et al., 2013). Here, we investigated whether this phenomenon can also be observed when non-frontal
 591 UP-states are targeted. To this aim, the mean values averaged across the first 200 ms following stimulus onset
 592 were extracted for the following parameters: amplitude at the target electrode, global field power, topographic
 593 consistency, as well as the mean correlation between the scalp EEG and the template maps (Figure 7). All but
 594 one parameter were significantly elevated after stimulation vs. sham for all target sites (all $p < .035$, except for
 595 the template correlation at CPz: $p = .223$). The fact that the algorithm precisely targeted states with specific

596 voltage distributions (see previous chapter) and the finding that stimulation vs. sham enhanced not only the
 597 voltage at the target electrode, but the strength of the electric field (GFP) and the correlation between the scalp
 598 EEG and the respective template maps strongly suggest that auditory stimulation briefly enhanced the the
 599 targeted local UP-state.

600

Figure 7: EEG response to stimulation vs. sham: a) mean voltage (ERP in μV), b) correlation of EEG maps with the template map (Template-corr), c) global field power (field strength in μV), and d) the consistency of targeted maps (Topo. consistency) averaged across the first 200 ms post stimulus onset separately for each target condition (Fz, C4, CPz) and for stimulation vs. sham. All parameters except one were significantly increased after stimulation compared to sham for all target sites (all $p < .035$, except for the template correlation at CPz: $p = .223$).

601 **5.2.3 Local stimulation induces a stereotypical auditory evoked slow oscillatory potential**

602 Visual inspection of the temporal evolution of scalp maps (Figure 8, bottom panel) and of the voltage
 603 of single channels for each experimental condition (Figure 8, top panel) suggested that highly distinct states
 604 were targeted at stimulus onset (stimulation and sham condition), but that auditory stimulation vs. sham induced
 605 a stereotypical auditory evoked slow oscillatory potential. Stimulation in each condition was followed by a
 606 frontal DOWN-state at about 0.5 s and a frontal UP-state at about 1 s after stimulus onset. TANOVA
 607 contrasting CSD estimates for stimulation vs. sham confirmed that stimulation induced distinct scalp maps
 608 starting from 0.28 s up to 1.89 s following stimulation onset for all templates (Fz: 0.28-1.65 s, C4: 0.32-1.89 s,
 609 CPz: 0.37-1.7s, all $p = .003$).

610 Importantly, no interactions between targets and stimulation vs. sham were observed, i.e. the
 611 stimulation induced changes did not significantly differ between target sites. This was suggested by the fact that
 612 the omnibus TANOVA with the factor target (Fz vs. C4 vs. CPz) performed on the difference between
 613 stimulation vs. sham yielded no significant cluster. This suggests that stimulation induced a similar slow
 614 oscillatory pattern irrespective of the target site.

615 Note that plots illustrate the results for ERPs computed on EEG data, but that statistics were performed
 616 on ERPs for CSD estimates. The qualitative pattern of results was highly similar between EEG and CSD data.

617

618

Figure 8: event-related responses (ERPs) to stimulation vs. sham; Upper panels: ERP over target electrodes (left) and over frontal electrodes (right) for all target sites (Fz, C4, Cpz) and conditions (stimulation vs. sham). Center panel: global field power (gfp) for all target sites and conditions. Global field power shows a stronger peak for stimulation vs. sham immediately after stimulus onset ($t = 0.1$ s) as well as strong induced responses about 0.5 s, 1 s, and 1.5 s after stimulation vs. sham. Lower panel: scalp maps for all target sites and conditions; Scalp maps confirm successful targeting of the target states (left column, normalized units) at stimulus onset ($t = 0$ s; highlighted at $t = 0.1$ s). Scalp maps further suggest that stimulation but not sham was followed by a stereotypical auditory evoked slow oscillatory potential with a DOWN-state at $t = 0.5$ s, and an UP-state at 1 s after stimulus onset. The EEG was averaged across ± 50 ms for each depicted time-point.

619 **5.2.4 Stimulation induces a spindle**

620 Event-related time-frequency analyses on CSD estimates revealed that click noise stimulation induced
 621 significant increases in theta activity at about 0.5 s and in spindle activity at about 1 s following stimulation
 622 onset in all conditions (sig. cluster for Fz ranging from -0.04-1.3 s for 2-21 Hz, $p = .002$; two clusters for CPz
 623 ranging from -0.04 to 1.92 s, 2-22 Hz, both $p < .012$; two clusters for CPz ranging from 0.08-1.52 s, 2-21 Hz,
 624 both $p < .014$; Figure 9). An ANOVA comparing the effect of stimulation vs. sham between target conditions
 625 yielded no significant cluster. This suggests that stimulation induced similar spectral changes across all three
 626 target sites.

627

Figure 9: Comparison of event related spectral power between sham and stimulation condition for all target sites. Left: spectral power (arbitrary unit); Right: topographical distribution of theta and spindle power, time window selected for high power. Cluster-based statistical analyses revealed a significant enhancement of the spectral power following stimulation compared to sham for each target site from around 0-1.5s and from 2-22 Hz (all $p < .014$), but these enhancements were not significantly different between target sites.

628

629 **5.2.5 Stimulation enhances post-stimulus phase-amplitude coupling**

630 Post-stimulus coupling between the phase of slow oscillations and the amplitudes of higher frequencies
631 was enhanced for stimulation vs. sham for all three target sites ($p < .018$; Figure 10). For Fz, coupling was
632 significantly enhanced for two clusters encompassing the phase of frequencies between 0.6 and 3.2 Hz and the
633 amplitude for frequencies between 4-10 Hz ($p = .018$) and 12-19 Hz ($p = .004$). For C4, coupling was enhanced
634 between phases for 0.4-3.6 Hz and amplitudes for 4-20 Hz ($p = .002$). For CPz, coupling was enhanced for
635 phases between 0.6-3.8 Hz and amplitudes from 4-19 Hz ($p = .002$).

636 The enhanced phase-amplitude coupling following stimulation was not significantly different between
637 target sites. An ANOVA with the factor target site (Fz, C4, CPz) performed on the difference between
638 stimulation vs. sham yielded no significant clusters.

639

Figure 10: Phase amplitude coupling (PAC) for stimulation and sham for all target conditions. Left: Comodulogram; Right: topographical distribution of PAC selected for delta*sigma coupling and for delta*theta coupling. Cluster-analysis revealed a significantly enhanced coupling of the phase of slow oscillations and the amplitudes of higher frequencies for stimulation vs. sham (for all three target sites, $p < .018$), but this enhancement was not significantly different between the target sites.

640

641

642

643

6 General discussion

644

645

646

647

648

649

650

651

652

653

654

655

656

657

We present a new closed-loop stimulation algorithm that allows targeting local, EEG-defined slow oscillation UP- and DOWN-states of human slow-wave sleep: the topographic targeting of slow oscillations algorithm (TOPOSO). The algorithm detects transitions into upcoming local UP- and DOWN-states based on the temporal evolution of the similarity between topographic maps of the real-time EEG and predefined template maps of the target states. In simulations on pre-recorded EEG data, the TOPOSO algorithm successfully targeted slow oscillatory UP- and DOWN-states at 12 distinct target sites with high temporal precision and topographic specificity. Importantly, the algorithm targeted UP- and DOWN states with higher topographic precision than conventional approaches which only operate on the voltage of single EEG channels. As a consequence, the TOPOSO algorithm targeted fewer, but topographically more homogeneous states. A within-subject sham controlled nap-study with three different target sites (Frontal (Fz), Right Central (C4), Centro-Parietal (Cpz)) confirmed that the algorithm allows targeting stimulation at local UP-states over different sites on the scalp in real time in vivo. The TOPOSO algorithm thus opens up a field of new opportunities by allowing researchers and clinicians to target and modulate local slow oscillations in humans using any kind of stimulation.

658

659

660

661

662

663

664

665

666

667

668

669

670

671

672

The high topographic specificity of the TOPOSO algorithm could help improve the efficacy of existing sleep modulation applications. Current applications successfully use slow oscillation phase-targeted sensory stimulation to enhance SWS and to thereby improve the associated memory (Ngo, Martinetz, et al., 2013; Ong et al., 2016, 2018), immune (Besedovsky et al., 2017; Grimaldi et al., 2019), and endocrine functions (Grimaldi et al., 2019), to boost consolidation of specific memories during sleep (Göldi et al., 2019; Shimizu et al., 2018), and to alter plasticity in the motor cortex (Fattinger et al., 2017). All these applications build on conventional closed-loop stimulation approaches which only operate on the voltage of single EEG channels and therefore target slow oscillations with heterogeneous topographies. Importantly, the topography of an electric field on the scalp mirrors the predominating neuronal network activity in the brain (Michel & Koenig, 2018; ZanESCO, 2020), i.e. the current global brain state. Due to its high specificity regarding both, the phase of slow oscillations, and the topography of the targeted electric field, the TOPOSO algorithm ensures that stimulation always targets a similar brain state. Using TOPOSO instead of conventional closed-loop algorithms could improve the impact of existing sleep modulation applications by a) ensuring that stimulation always targets the relevant brain state, and by b) reducing unwanted side effects induced by incorrect modulation of non-target states.

673

674

675

676

677

678

679

680

681

The TOPOSO algorithm could further be used to modulate slow-oscillatory activity outside of NREM sleep. Although slow oscillations are a defining feature of SWS (Iber et al., 2007), similar oscillations can occur in rapid eye movement (REM) sleep (Bernardi et al., 2019; Bernardi & Siclari, 2019) and even during wakefulness (Andrillon et al., 2021; Avvenuti et al., 2021; Brokaw et al., 2016; Frohlich et al., 2021; Sattari et al., 2019). Importantly, slow oscillations in the awake brain are a sign of reduced attention (Andrillon et al., 2021) and alertness (Quercia et al., 2018). They further serve as biomarker of neuropathology after brain injury (Cassidy et al., 2020; Sarasso et al., 2020) or in epilepsy (Lundstrom et al., 2019), and they are associated with various neurological and psychiatric conditions (Frohlich et al., 2021). Slow-oscillatory activity in the awake brain is thus a promising target for modulation in health and disease. Unfortunately, slow oscillations have much

682 lower amplitudes in REM sleep and during wakefulness than in SWS (e.g. Andrillon et al., 2021). Conventional
683 approaches for phase targeted closed-loop stimulation may fail during REM sleep and wakefulness because they
684 detect slow oscillations based on their high amplitudes. The TOPOSO algorithm does not depend on specific
685 amplitude thresholds for detecting slow oscillations and further ensures that targeted UP- and DOWN-states are
686 topographically homogeneous. TOPOSO thus seems more suitable than conventional methods for modulating
687 slow oscillations in the awake brain and in REM sleep.

688 Furthermore, the TOPOSO algorithm opens new ways of customizing sleep modulation to specific sub-
689 groups of the population or to single individuals who show slow oscillations with unique topographic
690 characteristics. In fact, the TOPOSO algorithm is able to target slow oscillations with unique topographic
691 characteristics because it uses predefined templates of the topographies of the targeted local UP- and DOWN-
692 states. These templates can be generated from available sleep recordings that are representative of the target
693 population, or even from recordings of single individuals. Customizing stimulation to specific subpopulations or
694 individuals is important because the topography of slow oscillatory activity varies substantially and
695 systematically between groups and individuals. For example, different individuals show distinct, stable, trait-
696 like topographic distributions of slow oscillatory activity (Markovic et al., 2018). Furthermore, the topography
697 of slow oscillations changes systematically throughout adolescence (Kurth et al., 2010, 2012; Ringli & Huber,
698 2011) and again with aging (Landolt & Borbély, 2001; Sprecher et al., 2016). Also, some clinical populations
699 such as patients suffering from depression (Tesler et al., 2016) show altered slow oscillation topographies.
700 Addressing these individual differences will help to increase the precision of slow oscillation targeting and
701 could boost the impact of sleep modulation (Henin et al., 2019; Papalambros et al., 2019; Schneider et al., 2020;
702 Wunderlin et al., 2021).

703 Successful modulation of local slow oscillations will ultimately depend not only on precise targeting of
704 relevant local UP- and DOWN-states, but also on the type of stimulation that is applied. Here, we explored how
705 auditory stimulation alters local slow oscillations during sleep. In a sham-controlled nap study, auditory click
706 noises were targeted at UP-states detected over the frontal, right sensorimotor, and centro-parietal cortex.
707 Stimulation briefly enhanced the specific local UP-state. In fact, the amplitude at the target site, the strength of
708 the electrical field on the scalp, and the topographic similarity between EEG scalp maps and the template maps
709 of the respective target states were all increased during the first 200 ms following stimulation vs. sham. Whether
710 this brief enhancement of the targeted UP-states is sufficient for altering or improving their functions remains to
711 be tested. Importantly, stimulation then elicited a frontal slow oscillation. For all target sites, the targeted local
712 UP-states were followed by a frontal DOWN-state at around 500 ms and a frontal upstate at about 900 ms after
713 stimulus onset. Earlier studies investigating auditory processing during sleep suggest that frontal slow
714 oscillations are the stereotypical brain response to auditory stimulation during sleep (Andrillon et al., 2016;
715 Andrillon & Kouider, 2020; Colrain & Campbell, 2007; Riedner et al., 2011; Ruch et al., 2014). This is also
716 suggested by the finding that specific targeting of local slow oscillations did not lead to a change in any of the
717 parameters that were assessed to study the neuronal response to auditory stimulation. None of the stimulus-
718 induced changes in electrical potentials, spectral power, or phase-amplitude coupling differed significantly
719 between target sites. We therefore conclude that entrainment of non-frontal, local slow oscillations might not be
720 possible with auditory stimulation. Whether the induced frontal slow-oscillation represents a general sleep-

721 preserving function of the brain that is triggered by any kind of sensory stimulation, (Andrillon et al., 2016) or
722 whether the initiation of frontal slow oscillations is specifically favored by the auditory pathway (Bellesi et al.,
723 2014) is beyond the scope of this paper.

724 Here, we speculate that optimal modulation of local slow oscillations is achieved through the use of
725 stimulation techniques that directly alter neuronal activity within the specific cortical site of interest. Such
726 techniques could include multisensory (e.g. audiovisual) stimulation, sensory stimulation in the specific
727 modality of the targeted sensori-motor cortical network (Bar et al., 2020; Laurino et al., 2019), transcutaneous
728 electrical nerve stimulation (Ravan & Begnaud, 2019; Veldman et al., 2021), or transcranial electrical (Ketz et
729 al., 2018), electromagnetic (Murphy et al., 2009), or even ultrasound stimulation (Fomenko et al., 2018).
730 Importantly, the TOPOSO algorithm allows steering any kind of stimulation for targeting local slow
731 oscillations.

732 With the appropriate type of stimulation, the TOPOSO algorithm can be used to either enhance and
733 entrain specific local slow oscillations, or to suppress them. Both enhancement and suppression might find use
734 in different practical applications. Enhancing local slow oscillations should increase their specific function. This
735 could, for example, help with recovery after brain injury. Animal research indeed suggests that artificial
736 enhancement of local slow oscillations in the peri-infarct zone after stroke boosts recovery (Facchin et al.,
737 2020). Admittedly, boosting of local slow oscillations might be more difficult to achieve than suppression. This
738 is suggested by the finding that auditory stimulation entrained stereotypical frontal instead of local, non-frontal
739 slow oscillations in this study. Selective suppression of specific local slow oscillations could allow studying
740 their function in general (Crupi et al., 2009; Fattinger et al., 2017). Perturbing specific local UP- and DOWN-
741 states could further find use in clinical applications where pathological subtypes of slow oscillations must be
742 suppressed. In depression, for example, frontal slow oscillatory activity tends to be enhanced during sleep
743 (Tesler et al., 2016). Suppressing these frontal slow oscillations was found to have an antidepressant effect
744 (Landsness et al., 2011). The TOPOSO algorithm could provide a means to selectively suppress frontal slow
745 oscillations while leaving other slow oscillatory activity intact. This could provide the desired antidepressant
746 effect while producing fewer unwanted side effects than standard sleep deprivation regimes that suppress all
747 slow oscillatory activity (Giedke & Schwärzler, 2002). The TOPOSO algorithm could further be used for
748 suppressing pathological slow oscillations in wakefulness after brain injury (Cassidy et al., 2020; Sarasso et al.,
749 2020) or in epilepsy (Lundstrom et al., 2019).

750 The TOPOSO algorithm and the presented findings are not without limitations. First of all, it is unclear
751 how well the algorithm would perform on different EEG equipment and in different environments. The EEG
752 data provided for the training of our algorithm, the data used for the simulation study, and the data acquired in
753 the closed-loop stimulation study were all recorded with the same equipment and in the same
754 electromagnetically shielded room. Recordings with different systems or in unshielded rooms might call for
755 heavy filtering and preprocessing of real-time data. This might affect the overall performance of the algorithm
756 or require adjustment of the settings and parameters. A further limitation is the small sample size of the in-vivo
757 validation study and the fact that stimulation was administered during a relatively short afternoon nap. More
758 stimulations across an entire night in a larger sample of participants might provide the statistical power that is
759 necessary for finding subtle differences in the slow oscillatory activity that is induced by stimulations targeted at

760 distinct local UP-states. Finally, the generalizability of our findings is limited by the fact that the simulations as
 761 well as the in-vivo stimulation were performed on afternoon naps. It is thus unclear how well the algorithm
 762 would perform on natural night sleep. Importantly, though, the algorithm is currently successfully used for
 763 targeting frontal UP- and DOWN-states during night sleep in several ongoing studies.

764 In sum, we argued that studies and applications aiming at modulating local slow oscillations during
 765 human sleep so far used closed-loop stimulation algorithms that failed to consistently target local slow
 766 oscillatory activity. We therefore introduced and validated a new EEG-based closed-loop algorithm that allows
 767 precise topographic targeting of local slow oscillations (TOPOSO) on different sites on the scalp. As the
 768 TOPOSO algorithm allows to target local slow oscillations based on predefined templates, it will enable
 769 individualized targeting of slow oscillations in sub populations with altered slow oscillatory activity. We used
 770 this algorithm in a closed-loop stimulation study and found that auditory stimulation targeted at local UP-states
 771 may briefly enhance the targeted state, but then induces frontal rather than local slow oscillations. Therefore, we
 772 suggest that future applications aiming at local slow oscillatory enhancements use stimulation modalities
 773 (tactile, olfactory, visual, gustatory stimulation; electric or magnetic non-invasive brain stimulation) that address
 774 the functional specialization of the cortical site of interest and thereby induce and entrain local slow oscillations.

775 7 References

- 776 Achermann, P., & Borbély, A. A. (1997). Low-frequency (<1 Hz) oscillations in the human sleep
 777 electroencephalogram. *Neuroscience*, *81*(1), 213–222. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0306-4522\(97\)00186-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0306-4522(97)00186-3)
- 778 Andrillon, T., Burns, A., Mackay, T., Windt, J., & Tsuchiya, N. (2021). Predicting lapses of attention with
 779 sleep-like slow waves. *Nature Communications*, *12*(1), 3657. [https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-23890-7)
 780 [23890-7](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-23890-7)
- 781 Andrillon, T., & Kouider, S. (2020). The vigilant sleeper: Neural mechanisms of sensory (de)coupling during
 782 sleep. *Current Opinion in Physiology*, *15*, 47–59. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cophys.2019.12.002>
- 783 Andrillon, T., Poulsen, A. T., Hansen, L. K., Léger, D., & Kouider, S. (2016). Neural markers of responsiveness
 784 to the environment in human sleep. *The Journal of Neuroscience*, *36*(24), 6583–6596.
 785 <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.0902-16.2016>
- 786 Avvenuti, G., & Bernardi, G. (2022). Chapter 3 - Local sleep: A new concept in brain plasticity. In A.
 787 Quartarone, M. F. Ghilardi, & F. Boller (Eds.), *Handbook of Clinical Neurology* (Vol. 184, pp. 35–52).
 788 Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-819410-2.00003-5>
- 789 Avvenuti, G., Bertelloni, D., Lettieri, G., Ricciardi, E., Cecchetti, L., Pietrini, P., & Bernardi, G. (2021).
 790 Emotion regulation failures are preceded by local increases in sleep-like activity. *Journal of Cognitive*
 791 *Neuroscience*, 1–15. https://doi.org/10.1162/jocn_a_01753
- 792 Bar, E., Marmelshtein, A., Arzi, A., Perl, O., Livne, E., Hizmi, E., Paz, R., Sobel, N., Dudai, Y., & Nir, Y.
 793 (2020). Local targeted memory reactivation in human sleep. *Current Biology*, *30*(8), 1435–1446.
 794 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2020.01.091>
- 795 Bellesi, M., Riedner, B. A., Garcia-Molina, G. N., Cirelli, C., & Tononi, G. (2014). Enhancement of sleep slow
 796 waves: Underlying mechanisms and practical consequences. *Frontiers in Systems Neuroscience*, *8*,
 797 208. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnsys.2014.00208>

- 798 Berens, P. (2009). CircStat: A MATLAB Toolbox for Circular Statistics. *Journal of Statistical Software*, 31(1),
799 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v031.i10>
- 800 Bernardi, G., Betta, M., Ricciardi, E., Pietrini, P., Tononi, G., & Siclari, F. (2019). Regional delta waves in
801 human rapid-eye movement sleep. *Journal of Neuroscience*, 2298–18.
802 <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.2298-18.2019>
- 803 Bernardi, G., & Siclari, F. (2019). Chapter 3—Local Patterns of Sleep and Wakefulness. In H. C. Dringenberg
804 (Ed.), *Handbook of Behavioral Neuroscience* (Vol. 30, pp. 33–47). Elsevier.
805 <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-813743-7.00003-7>
- 806 Bernardi, G., Siclari, F., Handjaras, G., Riedner, B. A., & Tononi, G. (2018). Local and widespread slow waves
807 in stable NREM sleep: Evidence for distinct regulation mechanisms. *Frontiers in Human*
808 *Neuroscience*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2018.00248>
- 809 Besedovsky, L., Lange, T., & Born, J. (2012). Sleep and immune function. *Pflügers Archiv European Journal of*
810 *Physiology*, 1–17.
- 811 Besedovsky, L., Ngo, H.-V. V., Dimitrov, S., Gassenmaier, C., Lehmann, R., & Born, J. (2017). Auditory
812 closed-loop stimulation of EEG slow oscillations strengthens sleep and signs of its immune-supportive
813 function. *Nature Communications*, 8(1), 1984. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-017-02170-3>
- 814 Bigdely-Shamlo, N., Mullen, T., Kothe, C., Su, K.-M., & Robbins, K. A. (2015). The PREP pipeline:
815 Standardized preprocessing for large-scale EEG analysis. *Frontiers in Neuroinformatics*, 9.
816 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fninf.2015.00016>
- 817 Brokaw, K., Tishler, W., Manceor, S., Hamilton, K., Gaulden, A., Parr, E., & Wamsley, E. J. (2016). Resting
818 state EEG correlates of memory consolidation. *Neurobiology of Learning and Memory*, 130, 17–25.
819 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nlm.2016.01.008>
- 820 Cassidy, J. M., Wodeyar, A., Wu, J., Kaur, K., Masuda, A. K., Srinivasan, R., & Cramer, S. C. (2020). Low-
821 frequency oscillations are a biomarker of injury and recovery after stroke. *Stroke*, 51(5), 1442–1450.
822 <https://doi.org/10.1161/STROKEAHA.120.028932>
- 823 Choi, J., Kwon, M., & Jun, S. C. (2020). A systematic review of closed-loop feedback techniques in sleep
824 studies—Related issues and future directions. *Sensors*, 20(10), 2770.
825 <https://doi.org/10.3390/s20102770>
- 826 Collins, D. L., Zijdenbos, A. P., Kollokian, V., Sled, J. G., Kabani, N. J., Holmes, C. J., & Evans, A. C. (1998).
827 Design and construction of a realistic digital brain phantom. *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging*,
828 17(3), 463–468. <https://doi.org/10.1109/42.712135>
- 829 Colrain, I. M., & Campbell, K. B. (2007). The use of evoked potentials in sleep research. *Sleep Medicine*
830 *Reviews*, 11(4), 277–293. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.smrv.2007.05.001>
- 831 Cox, R., Korjoukov, I., de Boer, M., & Talamini, L. M. (2014). Sound asleep: Processing and retention of slow
832 oscillation phase-targeted stimuli. *PLoS ONE*, 9(7), e101567.
833 <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0101567>
- 834 Crupi, D., Hulse, B. K., Peterson, M. J., Huber, R., Ansari, H., Coen, M., Cirelli, C., Benca, R. M., Ghilardi, M.
835 F., & Tononi, G. (2009). Sleep-dependent improvement in visuomotor learning: A causal role for slow
836 waves. *Sleep*, 32(10), 1273–1284. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sleep/32.10.1273>
- 837 Danilenko, K. V., Kobelev, E., Yarosh, S. V., Khazankin, G. R., Brack, I. V., Miroshnikova, P. V., & Aftanas,

- 838 L. I. (2020). Effectiveness of visual vs. Acoustic closed-loop stimulation on EEG power density during
 839 NREM sleep in humans. *Clocks & Sleep*, 2(2), 172–181. <https://doi.org/10.3390/clockssleep2020014>
- 840 Delorme, A., & Makeig, S. (2004). EEGLAB: An open source toolbox for analysis of single-trial EEG
 841 dynamics including independent component analysis. *Journal of Neuroscience Methods*, 134(1), 9–21.
 842 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jneumeth.2003.10.009>
- 843 Diaz Hernandez, L., Rieger, K., Baenninger, A., Brandeis, D., & Koenig, T. (2016). Towards using microstate-
 844 neurofeedback for the treatment of psychotic symptoms in schizophrenia. A feasibility study in healthy
 845 participants. *Brain Topography*, 29(2), 308–321. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10548-015-0460-4>
- 846 Facchin, L., Schöne, C., Mensen, A., Bandarabadi, M., Pilotto, F., Saxena, S., Libourel, P. A., Bassetti, C. L. A.,
 847 & Adamantidis, A. R. (2020). Slow waves promote sleep-dependent plasticity and functional recovery
 848 after stroke. *Journal of Neuroscience*, 40(45), 8637–8651. [https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.0373-](https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.0373-20.2020)
 849 20.2020
- 850 Fattinger, S., Beukelaar, T. T. de, Ruddy, K. L., Volk, C., Heyse, N. C., Herbst, J. A., Hahnloser, R. H. R.,
 851 Wenderoth, N., & Huber, R. (2017). Deep sleep maintains learning efficiency of the human brain.
 852 *Nature Communications*, 8, 15405. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms15405>
- 853 Finelli, L. A., Borbély, A. A., & Achermann, P. (2001). Functional topography of the human nonREM sleep
 854 electroencephalogram. *European Journal of Neuroscience*, 13(12), 2282–2290.
 855 <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.0953-816x.2001.01597.x>
- 856 Fomenko, A., Neudorfer, C., Dallapiazza, R. F., Kalia, S. K., & Lozano, A. M. (2018). Low-intensity ultrasound
 857 neuromodulation: An overview of mechanisms and emerging human applications. *Brain Stimulation*,
 858 11(6), 1209–1217. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brs.2018.08.013>
- 859 Frohlich, J., Toker, D., & Monti, M. M. (2021). Consciousness among delta waves: A paradox? *Brain*,
 860 awab095. <https://doi.org/10.1093/brain/awab095>
- 861 Geiser, T., Hertenstein, E., Fehér, K., Maier, J. G., Schneider, C. L., Züst, M. A., Wunderlin, M., Mikutta, C.,
 862 Klöppel, S., & Nissen, C. (2020). Targeting Arousal and Sleep through Noninvasive Brain Stimulation
 863 to Improve Mental Health. *Neuropsychobiology*, 79(4), 284–292. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000507372>
- 864 Giedke, H., & Schwärzler, F. (2002). Therapeutic use of sleep deprivation in depression. *Sleep Medicine*
 865 *Reviews*, 6(5), 361–377. <https://doi.org/10.1053/smr.2002.0235>
- 866 Göldi, M., Poppel, E. A. M. van, Rasch, B., & Schreiner, T. (2019). Increased neuronal signatures of targeted
 867 memory reactivation during slow-wave up states. *Scientific Reports*, 9(1), 2715.
 868 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-39178-2>
- 869 Grimaldi, D., Papalambros, N. A., Reid, K. J., Abbott, S. M., Malkani, R. G., Gendy, M., Iwanaszko, M., Braun,
 870 R. I., Sanchez, D. J., Paller, K. A., & Zee, P. C. (2019). Strengthening sleep–autonomic interaction via
 871 acoustic enhancement of slow oscillations. *Sleep*, 42(zsz036). <https://doi.org/10.1093/sleep/zsz036>
- 872 Grimaldi, D., Papalambros, N. A., Zee, P. C., & Malkani, R. G. (2020). Neurostimulation techniques to enhance
 873 sleep and improve cognition in aging. *Neurobiology of Disease*, 104865.
 874 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nbd.2020.104865>
- 875 Henin, S., Borges, H., Shankar, A., Sarac, C., Melloni, L., Friedman, D., Flinker, A., Parra, L. C., Buzsaki, G.,
 876 Devinsky, O., & Liu, A. (2019). Closed-loop acoustic stimulation enhances sleep oscillations but not
 877 memory performance. *ENeuro*, ENEURO.0306-19.2019. [34/43](https://doi.org/10.1523/ENEURO.0306-</p>
</div>
<div data-bbox=)

- 878 19.2019
- 879 Huber, R., Ghilardi, M. F., Massimini, M., Ferrarelli, F., Riedner, B. A., Peterson, M. J., & Tononi, G. (2006).
880 Arm immobilization causes cortical plastic changes and locally decreases sleep slow wave activity.
881 *Nature Neuroscience*, 9(9), 1169–1176. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nn1758>
- 882 Huber, R., Ghilardi, M. F., Massimini, M., & Tononi, G. (2004). Local sleep and learning. *Nature*, 430(6995),
883 78–81. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature02663>
- 884 Iber, C., Ancoli-Israel, S., Chesson, A., & Quan, S. F. (2007). *The AASM manual for the scoring of sleep and*
885 *associated events: Rules, terminology and technical specifications*. (1st ed.). American Academy of
886 Sleep Medicine.
- 887 Kayser, J., & Tenke, C. E. (2015). On the benefits of using surface Laplacian (current source density)
888 methodology in electrophysiology. *International Journal of Psychophysiology*, 97(3), 171–173.
889 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpsycho.2015.06.001>
- 890 Ketz, N., Jones, A. P., Bryant, N. B., Clark, V. P., & Pilly, P. K. (2018). Closed-Loop Slow-Wave tACS
891 Improves Sleep-Dependent Long-Term Memory Generalization by Modulating Endogenous
892 Oscillations. *Journal of Neuroscience*, 38(33), 7314–7326. [https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.0273-](https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.0273-18.2018)
893 18.2018
- 894 Klinzing, J. G., Niethard, N., & Born, J. (2019). Mechanisms of systems memory consolidation during sleep.
895 *Nature Neuroscience*, 22(10), 1598–1610. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41593-019-0467-3>
- 896 Koenig, T., Kottlow, M., Stein, M., & Melie-García, L. (2011). Ragu: A free tool for the analysis of EEG and
897 MEG event-related scalp field data using global randomization statistics. *Computational Intelligence*
898 *and Neuroscience*, 2011, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2011/938925>
- 899 Koenig, T., Stein, M., Grieder, M., & Kottlow, M. (2013). A tutorial on data-driven methods for statistically
900 assessing ERP topographies. *Brain Topography*, 27(1), 72–83. [https://doi.org/10.1007/s10548-013-](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10548-013-0310-1)
901 0310-1
- 902 Krugliakova, E., Volk, C., Jaramillo, V., Sousouri, G., & Huber, R. (2020). Changes in cross-frequency
903 coupling following closed-loop auditory stimulation in non-rapid eye movement sleep. *Scientific*
904 *Reports*, 10(1), 10628. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-67392-w>
- 905 Kurth, S., Ringli, M., Geiger, A., LeBourgeois, M., Jenni, O. G., & Huber, R. (2010). Mapping of cortical
906 activity in the first two decades of life: A high-density sleep electroencephalogram study. *Journal of*
907 *Neuroscience*, 30(40), 13211–13219. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.2532-10.2010>
- 908 Kurth, S., Ringli, M., LeBourgeois, M. K., Geiger, A., Buchmann, A., Jenni, O. G., & Huber, R. (2012).
909 Mapping the electrophysiological marker of sleep depth reveals skill maturation in children and
910 adolescents. *NeuroImage*, 63(2), 959–965. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2012.03.053>
- 911 Landolt, H.-P., & Borbély, A. A. (2001). Age-dependent changes in sleep EEG topography. *Clinical*
912 *Neurophysiology*, 112(2), 369–377. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1388-2457\(00\)00542-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1388-2457(00)00542-3)
- 913 Landsness, E. C., Goldstein, M. R., Peterson, M. J., Tononi, G., & Benca, R. M. (2011). Antidepressant effects
914 of selective slow wave sleep deprivation in major depression: A high-density EEG investigation.
915 *Journal of Psychiatric Research*, 45(8), 1019–1026. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpsychires.2011.02.003>
- 916 Laurino, M., Piarulli, A., Menicucci, D., & Gemignani, A. (2019). Local gamma activity during non-rem sleep
917 in the context of sensory evoked k-complexes. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, 13.

- 918 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2019.01094>
- 919 Llorens, F., Zarranz, J.-J., Fischer, A., Zerr, I., & Ferrer, I. (2017). Fatal Familial Insomnia: Clinical Aspects
 920 and Molecular Alterations. *Current Neurology and Neuroscience Reports*, 17(4), 30.
 921 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11910-017-0743-0>
- 922 Lundstrom, B. N., Boly, M., Duckrow, R., Zaveri, H. P., & Blumenfeld, H. (2019). Slowing less than 1 Hz is
 923 decreased near the seizure onset zone. *Scientific Reports*, 9(1), 6218. [https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-42347-y)
 924 [019-42347-y](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-42347-y)
- 925 Mak-McCully, R. A., Rosen, B. Q., Rolland, M., Régis, J., Bartolomei, F., Rey, M., Chauvel, P., Cash, S. S., &
 926 Halgren, E. (2015). Distribution, amplitude, incidence, co-occurrence, and propagation of human K-
 927 complexes in focal transcortical recordings. *ENeuro*, 2(4). [https://doi.org/10.1523/ENEURO.0028-](https://doi.org/10.1523/ENEURO.0028-15.2015)
 928 [15.2015](https://doi.org/10.1523/ENEURO.0028-15.2015)
- 929 Mander, B. A., Rao, V., Lu, B., Saletin, J. M., Lindquist, J. R., Ancoli-Israel, S., Jagust, W., & Walker, M. P.
 930 (2013). Prefrontal atrophy, disrupted NREM slow waves and impaired hippocampal-dependent
 931 memory in aging. *Nature Neuroscience*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nn.3324>
- 932 Mander, B. A., Winer, J. R., & Walker, M. P. (2017). Sleep and human aging. *Neuron*, 94(1), 19–36.
 933 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2017.02.004>
- 934 Maris, E., & Oostenveld, R. (2007). Nonparametric statistical testing of EEG- and MEG-data. *Journal of*
 935 *Neuroscience Methods*, 164(1), 177–190. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jneumeth.2007.03.024>
- 936 Markovic, A., Achermann, P., Rusterholz, T., & Tarokh, L. (2018). Heritability of sleep EEG topography in
 937 adolescence: Results from a longitudinal twin study. *Scientific Reports*, 8(1), 7334.
 938 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-25590-7>
- 939 Mascetti, L., Muto, V., Matarazzo, L., Foret, A., Ziegler, E., Albouy, G., Sterpenich, V., Schmidt, C.,
 940 Degueldre, C., Leclercq, Y., Phillips, C., Luxen, A., Vandewalle, G., Vogels, R., Maquet, P., &
 941 Balteau, E. (2013). The impact of visual perceptual learning on sleep and local slow-wave initiation.
 942 *The Journal of Neuroscience*, 33(8), 3323–3331. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.0763-12.2013>
- 943 Massimini, M., Huber, R., Ferrarelli, F., Hill, S., & Tononi, G. (2004). The sleep slow oscillation as a traveling
 944 wave. *The Journal of Neuroscience*, 24(31), 6862–6870. [https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.1318-](https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.1318-04.2004)
 945 [04.2004](https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.1318-04.2004)
- 946 McHugh, M. L. (2012). Interrater reliability: The kappa statistic. *Biochemia Medica*, 276–282.
 947 <https://doi.org/10.11613/BM.2012.031>
- 948 Michel, C. M., & Koenig, T. (2018). EEG microstates as a tool for studying the temporal dynamics of whole-
 949 brain neuronal networks: A review. *NeuroImage*, 180, 577–593.
 950 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2017.11.062>
- 951 Murphy, M., Riedner, B. A., Huber, R., Massimini, M., Ferrarelli, F., & Tononi, G. (2009). Source modeling
 952 sleep slow waves. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 106(5), 1608–1613.
 953 <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0807933106>
- 954 Ngo, H.-V. V., Claussen, J. C., Born, J., & Mölle, M. (2013). Induction of slow oscillations by rhythmic
 955 acoustic stimulation. *Journal of Sleep Research*, 22(1), 22–31. [https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2869.2012.01039.x)
 956 [2869.2012.01039.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2869.2012.01039.x)
- 957 Ngo, H.-V. V., Martinetz, T., Born, J., & Mölle, M. (2013). Auditory closed-loop stimulation of the sleep slow

- 958 oscillation enhances memory. *Neuron*, 78(3), 545–553. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2013.03.006>
- 959 Ngo, H.-V. V., Miedema, A., Faude, I., Martinetz, T., Mölle, M., & Born, J. (2015). Driving sleep slow
 960 oscillations by auditory closed-loop stimulation—A self-limiting process. *The Journal of*
 961 *Neuroscience*, 35(17), 6630–6638. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.3133-14.2015>
- 962 Nir, Y., Staba, R. J., Andrillon, T., Vyazovskiy, V. V., Cirelli, C., Fried, I., & Tononi, G. (2011). Regional slow
 963 waves and spindles in human sleep. *Neuron*, 70(1), 153–169.
 964 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2011.02.043>
- 965 Ong, J. L., Lo, J. C., Chee, N. I. Y. N., Santostasi, G., Paller, K. A., Zee, P. C., & Chee, M. W. L. (2016).
 966 Effects of phase-locked acoustic stimulation during a nap on EEG spectra and declarative memory
 967 consolidation. *Sleep Medicine*, 20, 88–97. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sleep.2015.10.016>
- 968 Ong, J. L., Patanaik, A., Chee, N. I. Y. N., Lee, X. K., Poh, J.-H., & Chee, M. W. L. (2018). Auditory
 969 stimulation of sleep slow oscillations modulates subsequent memory encoding through altered
 970 hippocampal function. *Sleep*, 41(5), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sleep/zsy031>
- 971 Oostenveld, R., Fries, P., Maris, E., & Schoffelen, J.-M. (2011). FieldTrip: Open Source Software for Advanced
 972 Analysis of MEG, EEG, and Invasive Electrophysiological Data. *Computational Intelligence and*
 973 *Neuroscience*, 2011, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2011/156869>
- 974 Oostenveld, R., Stegeman, D. F., Praamstra, P., & van Oosterom, A. (2003). Brain symmetry and topographic
 975 analysis of lateralized event-related potentials. *Clinical Neurophysiology*, 114(7), 1194–1202.
 976 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1388-2457\(03\)00059-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1388-2457(03)00059-2)
- 977 Papalambros, N. A., Santostasi, G., Malkani, R. G., Braun, R., Weintraub, S., Paller, K. A., & Zee, P. C. (2017).
 978 Acoustic enhancement of sleep slow oscillations and concomitant memory improvement in older
 979 adults. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2017.00109>
- 980 Papalambros, N. A., Weintraub, S., Chen, T., Grimaldi, D., Santostasi, G., Paller, K. A., Zee, P. C., & Malkani,
 981 R. G. (2019). Acoustic enhancement of sleep slow oscillations in mild cognitive impairment. *Annals of*
 982 *Clinical and Translational Neurology*, 6(7), 1191–1201. <https://doi.org/10.1002/acn3.796>
- 983 Perrin, F., Pernier, J., Bertrand, O., & Echallier, J. F. (1989). Spherical splines for scalp potential and current
 984 density mapping. *Electroencephalography and Clinical Neurophysiology*, 72(2), 184–187.
 985 [https://doi.org/10.1016/0013-4694\(89\)90180-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0013-4694(89)90180-6)
- 986 Perrin, F., Pernier, J., Bertrand, O., & Echallier, J. F. (1990). Corrigenda. *Electroencephalography and Clinical*
 987 *Neurophysiology*, 76(6), 565–566. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0013-4694\(90\)90009-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0013-4694(90)90009-9)
- 988 Quercia, A., Zappasodi, F., Comitteri, G., & Ferrara, M. (2018). Local use-dependent sleep in wakefulness
 989 links performance errors to learning. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*, 12, 122.
 990 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2018.00122>
- 991 Rasch, B., & Born, J. (2013). About sleep’s role in memory. *Physiological Reviews*, 93(2), 681–766.
 992 <https://doi.org/10.1152/physrev.00032.2012>
- 993 Ravan, M., & Begnaud, J. (2019). Investigating the effect of short term responsive VNS therapy on sleep quality
 994 using automatic sleep staging. *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering*, 66(12), 3301–3309.
 995 <https://doi.org/10.1109/TBME.2019.2903987>
- 996 Rechtschaffen, A., Bergmann, B. M., Everson, C. A., Kushida, C. A., & Gilliland, M. A. (2002). Sleep
 997 Deprivation in the Rat: X. Integration and Discussion of the Findings. *Sleep*, 25(1), 68–87.

- 998 <https://doi.org/10.1093/sleep/25.1.68>
- 999 Renard, Y., Lotte, F., Gibert, G., Congedo, M., Maby, E., Delannoy, V., Bertrand, O., & Lécuyer, A. (2010).
1000 OpenViBE: An Open-Source Software Platform to Design, Test, and Use Brain–Computer Interfaces
1001 in Real and Virtual Environments. *Presence: Teleoperators and Virtual Environments*, 19(1), 35–53.
1002 <https://doi.org/10.1162/pres.19.1.35>
- 1003 Riedner, B. A., Hulse, B. K., Murphy, M. J., Ferrarelli, F., & Tononi, G. (2011). Temporal dynamics of cortical
1004 sources underlying spontaneous and peripherally evoked slow waves. *Progress in Brain Research*, 193,
1005 201–218. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-53839-0.00013-2>
- 1006 Riedner, B. A., Vyazovskiy, V. V., Huber, R., Massimini, M., Esser, S., Murphy, M., & Tononi, G. (2007).
1007 Sleep Homeostasis and Cortical Synchronization: III. A High-Density EEG Study of Sleep Slow
1008 Waves in Humans. *Sleep*, 30(12), 1643–1657. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sleep/30.12.1643>
- 1009 Ringli, M., & Huber, R. (2011). Chapter 5 - Developmental aspects of sleep slow waves: Linking sleep, brain
1010 maturation and behavior. In E. J. W. Van Someren, Y. D. Van Der Werf, P. R. Roelfsema, H. D.
1011 Mansvelder, & F. H. Lopes Da Silva (Eds.), *Progress in Brain Research* (Vol. 193, pp. 63–82).
1012 Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-53839-0.00005-3>
- 1013 Ruch, S., Koenig, T., Mathis, J., Roth, C., & Henke, K. (2014). Word encoding during sleep is suggested by
1014 correlations between word-evoked up-states and post-sleep semantic priming. *Frontiers in Psychology*,
1015 5, 1319. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2014.01319>
- 1016 Santostasi, G., Malkani, R., Riedner, B., Bellesi, M., Tononi, G., Paller, K. A., & Zee, P. C. (2016). Phase-
1017 locked loop for precisely timed acoustic stimulation during sleep. *Journal of Neuroscience Methods*,
1018 259, 101–114. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jneumeth.2015.11.007>
- 1019 Sarasso, S., D’Ambrosio, S., Fecchio, M., Casarotto, S., Viganò, A., Landi, C., Mattavelli, G., Gosseries, O.,
1020 Quarengi, M., Laureys, S., Devalle, G., Rosanova, M., & Massimini, M. (2020). Local sleep-like
1021 cortical reactivity in the awake brain after focal injury. *Brain*, 143(12), 3672–3684.
1022 <https://doi.org/10.1093/brain/awaa338>
- 1023 Sattari, N., Whitehurst, L. N., Ahmadi, M., & Mednick, S. C. (2019). Does working memory improvement
1024 benefit from sleep in older adults? *Neurobiology of Sleep and Circadian Rhythms*, 6, 53–61.
1025 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nbscr.2019.01.001>
- 1026 Schabus, M., Dang-Vu, T. T., Heib, D. P. J., Boly, M., Desseilles, M., Vandewalle, G., Schmidt, C., Darsaud,
1027 A., Gais, S., Phillips, C., & Maquet, P. (2012). The fate of incoming stimuli during NREM sleep is
1028 determined by spindles and the phase of the slow oscillation. *Frontiers in Sleep and Chronobiology*, 3,
1029 40. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fneur.2012.00040>
- 1030 Schneider, J., Lewis, P. A., Koester, D., Born, J., & Ngo, H.-V. V. (2020). Susceptibility to auditory closed-loop
1031 stimulation of sleep slow oscillations changes with age. *Sleep*, 43(zsaa111).
1032 <https://doi.org/10.1093/sleep/zsaa111>
- 1033 Scholes, S., Santisteban, J. A., Zhang, Y., Bertone, A., & Gruber, R. (2020). Modulation of slow-wave sleep:
1034 Implications for psychiatry. *Current Psychiatry Reports*, 22(10), 52. [https://doi.org/10.1007/s11920-](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11920-020-01175-y)
1035 020-01175-y
- 1036 Shimizu, R. E., Connolly, P. M., Cellini, N., Armstrong, D. M., Hernandez, L. T., Estrada, R., Aguilar, M.,
1037 Weisend, M. P., Mednick, S. C., & Simons, S. B. (2018). Closed-loop targeted memory reactivation

- 1038 during sleep improves spatial navigation. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*, 12, 28.
 1039 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2018.00028>
- 1040 Siclari, F., Baird, B., Perogamvros, L., Bernardi, G., LaRocque, J. J., Riedner, B., Boly, M., Postle, B. R., &
 1041 Tononi, G. (2017). The neural correlates of dreaming. *Nature Neuroscience*, advance online
 1042 publication. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nn.4545>
- 1043 Siclari, F., Bernardi, G., Cataldi, J., & Tononi, G. (2018). Dreaming in NREM sleep: A high-density EEG study
 1044 of slow waves and spindles. *Journal of Neuroscience*, 38(43), 9175–9185.
 1045 <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.0855-18.2018>
- 1046 Sousouri, G., Krugliakova, E., Skorucak, J., Leach, S., Snipes, S., Ferster, M. L., Da Poian, G., Karlen, W., &
 1047 Huber, R. (2021). Neuromodulation by means of phase-locked auditory stimulation affects key marker
 1048 of excitability and connectivity during sleep. *Sleep*, zsab204. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sleep/zsab204>
- 1049 Sprecher, K. E., Riedner, B. A., Smith, R. F., Tononi, G., Davidson, R. J., & Benca, R. M. (2016). High
 1050 resolution topography of age-related changes in non-rapid eye movement sleep
 1051 electroencephalography. *PLOS ONE*, 11(2), e0149770. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0149770>
- 1052 Talamini, L. M., & Juan, E. (2020). Sleep as a window to treat affective disorders. *Current Opinion in*
 1053 *Behavioral Sciences*, 33, 99–108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cobeha.2020.02.002>
- 1054 Tesler, N., Gerstenberg, M., Franscini, M., Jenni, O. G., Walitza, S., & Huber, R. (2016). Increased frontal sleep
 1055 slow wave activity in adolescents with major depression. *NeuroImage: Clinical*, 10, 250–256.
 1056 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nicl.2015.10.014>
- 1057 Tononi, G., & Cirelli, C. (2020). Sleep and synaptic down-selection. *European Journal of Neuroscience*, 51(1),
 1058 413–421. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejn.14335>
- 1059 van Driel, J., Cox, R., & Cohen, M. X. (2015). Phase-clustering bias in phase–amplitude cross-frequency
 1060 coupling and its removal. *Journal of Neuroscience Methods*, 254, 60–72.
 1061 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jneumeth.2015.07.014>
- 1062 Veldman, M. P., Dolfen, N., Gann, M. A., Carrier, J., King, B. R., & Albouy, G. (2021). Somatosensory
 1063 targeted memory reactivation modulates oscillatory brain activity but not motor memory consolidation.
 1064 *Neuroscience*, 465, 203–218. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroscience.2021.03.027>
- 1065 Vyazovskiy, V. V., & Harris, K. D. (2013). Sleep and the single neuron: The role of global slow oscillations in
 1066 individual cell rest. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 14(6), 443–451. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrn3494>
- 1067 Wunderlin, M., Züst, M. A., Hertenstein, E., Fehér, K. D., Schneider, C. L., Klöppel, S., & Nissen, C. (2021).
 1068 Modulating overnight memory consolidation by acoustic stimulation during slow wave sleep – a
 1069 systematic review and meta-analysis. *Sleep*, zsa296. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sleep/zsa296>
- 1070 Xie, L., Kang, H., Xu, Q., Chen, M. J., Liao, Y., Thiyagarajan, M., O’Donnell, J., Christensen, D. J., Nicholson,
 1071 C., Iliff, J. J., Takano, T., Deane, R., & Nedergaard, M. (2013). Sleep Drives Metabolite Clearance
 1072 from the Adult Brain. *Science*, 342(6156), 373–377. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1241224>
- 1073 Zada, D., Bronshtein, I., Lerer-Goldshtein, T., Garini, Y., & Appelbaum, L. (2019). Sleep increases
 1074 chromosome dynamics to enable reduction of accumulating DNA damage in single neurons. *Nature*
 1075 *Communications*, 10(1), 895. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-08806-w>
- 1076 Zanesco, A. P. (2020). EEG electric field topography is stable during moments of high field strength. *Brain*
 1077 *Topography*, 33(4), 450–460. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10548-020-00780-7>

1078 Zar, J. H. (1999). *Biostatistical analysis* (4th ed.). Prentice-Hall.
1079 Züst, M. A., Ruch, S., Wiest, R., & Henke, K. (2019). Implicit vocabulary learning during sleep is bound to
1080 slow-wave peaks. *Current Biology*, 29(4), 541–553. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2018.12.038>

1081 **8 Acknowledgements**

1082 This work was supported by the Interfaculty Research Cooperation grant “Decoding Sleep: From
1083 Neurons to Health & Mind” of the University of Bern.

1084 **9 Author contributions**

1085 **Simon Ruch:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation,
1086 Data curation, Writing - Original Draft, Visualization, Supervision, Project Administration; **Flavio Jean**
1087 **Schmidig:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization,
1088 Supervision, Project Administration; **Leona Knüsel:** Investigation, Data Curation, Writing - Review & Editing,
1089 Visualization; **Katharina Henke:** Conceptualization, Resources, Writing – Review & Editing, Supervision,
1090 Project administration, Funding acquisition.

1091 **10 Declaration of interest**

1092 The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

1093 **11 Data availability**

1094 The relevant code and data for this research will be made available on <https://osf.io/> upon publication
1095 of this article.

1096

1097

1098

12 Supplementary Figures

1099

Supplemental Figure 1: Topographies of each targeted DOWN-state (template map in normalized units, left) and the average EEG topography over all trials displayed from 0.4s before to 0.4s after the detection of a transition ($t=0$), separately for each target site (ERP in μV). The EEG was averaged across ± 50 ms for each depicted time-point. The high similarity of the template map and the targeted brain state 200 ms (highlighted) after the detection of a transition suggests precise targeting of local DOWN-states.

1100

MODULATION OF LOCAL SLOW OSCILLATIONS

1101

Supplemental Figure 2: Event-related EEG activity relative to the detection of the transition ($t = 0$) into a local DOWN-state for each of the twelve target sites (color coded). Event-related potential (μV) at the target site (left panel), correlation of the EEG with the template map (middle panel), and global field power (GFP in μV) of the EEG. The ERP and the correlation with the template map reveal a similar prediction for each of the twelve target sites. Grey shades mark the time window (100 ms - 300 ms post transition) used for the analysis of the peak EEG.

1102

MODULATION OF LOCAL SLOW OSCILLATIONS

1103

Supplemental Figure 3: Comparison between the template-based TOPOSO algorithm (Template) and a conventional single-EEG-channel-based (EEG) algorithm for DOWN-state targeting. Mean voltage (ERP in μV) at the target site (mean over adjacent electrodes), correlation between EEG scalp map and template map, and global field power (all averaged across the time window from 0.1. to 0.3 s after detection of a transition) as well as the number of predicted states per minute. Each panel displays mean and standard error of the mean (error bars) for each target site. All paired-samples contrasts for each target were significant at $p < .003$.

1104